

Deliverable 2.5 – WP2. Report of EURAKNOS Workshop 1

EURAKNOS

*Connecting Thematic Networks as Knowledge Reservoirs towards a European Agricultural Knowledge
Innovation Open Source System*

TASK 2.5

Summary

WP2 aims to make an evaluation of past and running Thematic Networks (TN) and other EIP-AGRI highly related activities (linked multi-actor approach (MAA) H2020 projects and relevant Operational Groups (OGs) as case studies). Particularly, Task 2.5 summarizes the results on the mapping of all TNs, which were analysed in detail in the practices and methodologies of tasks 2.1, 2.2, 2.3 and 2.4. In these tasks, content collection (type of content and way to collect) and output creation was looked at in 2.1, output storage and Knowledge Reservoir (KR) in 2.2, communication & dissemination strategies (tools, formats and channels) in 2.3, and MAA (types and ways in which multi-actors are involved) in 2.4. The summary of all this work was discussed in a participatory 2-day workshop on TN impact assessment in Budapest (11-13 September 2019) with members of the Knowledge Innovation Panel (KIP) amongst which the coordinators of TNs, linked OGs, foresters, farmers and advisors to exchange experiences and know how between the different TNs. The report discusses the results of the workshop and 20 recommendations are put forward as a basis for quantitative and qualitative impact criteria (D2.6) and guidelines for successful TNs to be developed in WP3.

Deliverable Number	Work Package
2.5	WP2
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Planned Delivery Date	Actual Delivery Date
November 2019	April 2020

Type of Deliverable	R	Document, report (excluding periodic and final reports)	X
	DEC	Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos	
	E	Ethics	

Dissemination Level	PU	Public	X
	CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium	

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

4D4F	Data Driven Dairy Decision For Farmers
ACTA	Association de Coordination Technique Agricole
AFINET	AgroForestry Innovation NETworks
AKIS	Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems
AU	Aarhus University
AUA	Agricultural University of Athens
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
C&D	Communication and Dissemination
DISARM	Disseminating Innovative Solutions for Antibiotic Resistance Management
EIP-Agri	Agricultural European Innovation Partnership
EV ILVO	Eigen Vermogen van het Instituut voor Landbouw- en Visserijonderzoek
e-KRP	electronic Knowledge Reservoir Platform
F2F	Farmer to Farmer
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GLZ	Gruenlandzetruel Niedersachsen/Bremen EV
HIKR	High Impact Knowledge Reservoir
IfA	Innovation for Agriculture
ICORFS	International Centre for Research in Organic Food Systems
IDELE	Institut de l'Elevage
IFOAM	International Federation of Organic Agriculture Movements European Union Regional Group
KR	Knowledge Reservoir
MA	Multi-actor
MAA	Multi-actor Approach
MS	Member States
NAIK	Nemzeti Agrárkutatási és Innovációs Központ
NAK	Magyar Agrar-, Elél miszergazdasági Es Videkfejlesztési Kamara
NRN	National Rural Network
OG	Operational Group
PLAID	Peer-to-Peer learning:accessing innovation through demonstration
PSKW	Proefstation voor de Groenteteelt Sint-Katelijne-Waver
RAU	Royal Agricultural University
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SEO	Search Engine Optimization
SKIN	Short supply chains Knowledge & Innovation Network
SME	Small and medium-sized enterprises
SWG	Strategic Working Group
TN	Thematic Network
UGent	Ghent University
USC	Universidad de Santiago de Compostela
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package

1. Objectives

Task 2.5 will summarize the results on the TN current practices and methodologies and will come up with quantitative and qualitative criteria for high impact TNs.

In a first step Task 2.5 (M8-M10) ‘Exchanging and compiling know how’, supported Task 2.1, Task 2.2, Task 2.3 and Task 2.4. Task 2.1 deals with the evaluation of the outputs/data produced by the desk-top-study and the survey of 28 TNs with regard to the data knowledge content and format. It was the first step to better understand the format and design of a TN knowledge reservoir (KR) (Task 2.2), C&D strategies (Task 2.3), and strategies for the MAA (Task 2.4).

In a second step a EURAKNOS participatory workshop is foreseen in Task 2.5 as to present the results of the previous WP2 Tasks and validate these with end users.

Based on the outcome of these results quantitative and qualitative impact criteria will be formulated (D2.6) as input for WP3 - Design of a High Impact Knowledge Reservoir (HIKR). The results will also be used as a basis for the Vision Paper of the Strategic Innovation Board (SIB) on the future of open source KRs and the policy paper on TNs to be developed with the SCAR Strategic Working Group (SWG) on Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS) (WP5).

2. Task members

Task 2.5 is lead by the Aarhus University (AU) and composed of 14 members (all EURAKNOS partners).

Table 1. Partners involved in the different Tasks of WP2 (in bold the task leaders).

Task	Partner													
	ACTA	IDELE	NAK	UGent	GLZ	USC	AU	PSKW	ARC	AUA	IFA	LFG	RAU	EV ILVO
2.1	X	X	X	X	X	X		X						
2.2	X	X	X	X		X	X			X				
2.3	X	X	X	X	X	X		X			X	X	X	
2.4	X	X	X	X	X		X		X					
2.5	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

3. Workshop on TN impact assessment

The first EURAKNOS participatory workshop was held in Budapest from 11-13 September 2019.

3.1. Aim

The aim of the workshop was twofold

- 1) **Present the summary of the results of WP2 and to discuss and validate these with the end users.** The workshop took place in Budapest from 11-13 September 2019.
- 2) **To come up with a basis to formulate quantitative and qualitative criteria for TNs** (impact framework assessment) **as input for WP3** (Design of a High Impact Knowledge Reservoir (HIKR))

3.2. Participants

In total 26 consortium members and 32 members of the Knowledge Innovation Panel (KIP) have attended the workshops. The KIP has been established by WP1 (Task 1.3) in collaboration with all the EURAKNOS consortium partners. The KIP is a dynamic list of experts belonging to different actor categories (applied research organisations, technical centres, advisory , centres, SMEs, consultancy, farmers, foresters, chambers of agriculture, farmer

organisations, research organisations, government authorities, educational institutions, universities, NGOs etc.) from 17 different MS (Belgium, The Netherlands, France Germany, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Estonia, Romania, Hungary, Italy, Greece, Denmark, Lithuania, Austria, Spain) and the UK. EURAKNOS has two categories of end users: 1) TNs and their networks/community including OGs and 2) the endusers or uptakers of outputs and results (practice oriented knowledge) of TNs in the field, farmers, foresters and advisors. Both end users groups are represented in the KIP. Based on their profile (actor type, country, level of expertise, EURAKNOS end user group) about 40 experts were invited of which 32 have attended the workshop. In total 26 consortium members have attended. In total 18 TNs were represented (Smart-AKIS¹, Winetwork², Inno4Grass³, OK-net Ecofeed⁴, SheepNET⁵, DISARM⁶, 4D4F⁷, OK-net ARABLE⁸, NUTRIMAN⁹, FERTINNOWA¹⁰, Hennovation¹¹, NEWBIE¹², EUPiG¹³, ENABLING¹⁴, Incredible¹⁵, AgriSpin¹⁶, SKIN¹⁷, and Best4Soil¹⁸).

Figure 1. Group picture of participants in the EURAKNOS 1 Workshop (Budapest, 11-13 September 2019)

¹ <https://www.smart-akis.com/>

² <http://www.winetwork.eu/>

³ <https://www.inno4grass.eu/en/>

⁴ <https://ok-net-ecofeed.eu/>

⁵ <http://www.sheepnet.network/>

⁶ <https://disarmproject.eu/>

⁷ <https://www.4d4f.eu/>

⁸ <http://www.ok-net-arable.eu/>

⁹ <https://nutriman.net/project>

¹⁰ <https://www.fertinnowa.com/>

¹¹ <http://www.hennovation.eu/>

¹² <http://www.newbie-academy.eu/>

¹³ <https://www.eupig.eu/>

¹⁴ <https://www.enabling-project.com/>

¹⁵ <https://www.incredibleforest.net/>

¹⁶ <https://agrispin.eu/>

¹⁷ <http://www.shortfoodchain.eu/>

¹⁸ <https://delphy.nl/en/research/best4soil/>

3.3. Methodology

In general the participatory workshop consisted of plenary sessions as introductory sessions on a certain aspects of the TN (content, design, C&D and MAA), the electronic Knowledge Reservoir Platform (e-KRP) and the ideal/future TN; and parallel working sessions for which the group each time was split in subgroups.

After a general plenary introduction, the group was divided in three working groups for a welcome exercise, and to define the main challenges in agriculture and forestry as well as the main challenges of TNs. Afterwards the participants were asked about their expectations on the workshop. In a following exercise participants reflected on the top priorities of an ideal TN.

After a presentation on dissemination and communication (Task 2.3) in plenary, three groups of participants were asked if they were able to reach their target audience and why they could/or could not. In a second exercise on communication and dissemination, the participants were presented with some examples of outputs of knowledge (the homepage of a TN-website, LinkedIn-post by a TN and a video by a TN) which was disseminated to end users. They had to comment on the channel, format and content and if these were suited for particular end users which were pre-defined (3 different profiles) and why it was or it wasn't. In a next session the three working groups had to brainstorm on the ways farmers and foresters communicate their needs to a TN, if the output of a TN is useful or if the e-KRP should be selective (if so based on which criteria) and on what and who determines the level of expertise to create and curate content, and who has to be responsible for transforming data and knowledge in a standardized TN/e-KRP format.

After a plenary presentation in data and content of TNs (Task 2.1) participants were again split in three parallel groups to brainstorm on the level of expertise which is needed to create or curate content.

In a following session the current design of KRs within TNs was presented (Task 2.3) and discussed in subgroups.

After a plenary introductory session on the MAA (Task 2.4) the next parallel workshop sessions were dedicated to the different ways to engage actors in a TN and participants had to reflect on the type of potential actors/end users.

For the last workshop, participants were split in nine groups. Each group had to reflect on a future TN, more specifically on which tasks the TN still would execute and which tasks can be outsourced bearing in mind that there would be a common TN platform with a standardised approach.

The workshop program is presented in ANNEX I, the presentations summarising Task 2.1, 2.2, 2.3 and 2.4 are in ANNEX II, the detailed methodology during the plenary and parallel session with the results per group are given in ANNEX III.

Below the summary of the results as outcome of the different WGs and (sub) workshops during the parallel sessions is presented and discussed.

3.4. Summary of results

1) Current challenges in agriculture and forestry

In summary, according to the participants, the main challenges in agriculture/forestry are related to:

- Adopting new technologies, innovation uptake in practice
- Cost of production and cost of innovation
- Climate change, in particular mitigation such as climate friendly production but also adaptation (e.g. new varieties)
- Sustainable food production (farmers and the environment: biodiversity, circular ecology)
- Generational renewal, attractiveness of the sector, social acceptance
- More value from products: connecting consumers to the production chain; business model of extensive farming
- Pests: output uncertainty

- Agroforestry
- Antibiotics
- Water use
- Soil care
- Digitization and precision farming
- Clear rules and policies
- Collecting data
- Sharing expertise

2) Main challenges for TNs

According to the participants the main challenges for TNs are:

- Better management
- Building trust, working together with consortium partners, finding partners that are active and motivated
- Reaching and understanding end users (e.g. consider feedback from farmers), how to best go from the theory to practice, understanding knowledge gaps
- Co-creating solutions and/or re-creating (collecting) knowledge: clear, end user-oriented focus, engagement and involvement of multiple actors, end users and in particular farmers including small farmers and underprivileged farmers, distance & language
- Communication vs. GDPR compliance
- Dissemination: spreading innovation (finding multipliers at national level), and new developments, using a common language for practical knowledge (translation between research and real-life application), search ability of output, relevance (creating useful information) and timing of results
- Measuring impact, uptake of results
- Sustainability of the TN, its knowledge and the project, longevity, reuse what's working in a TN (sharing TN best practices)
- Time (challenging timeline)
- Different country needs, common understanding between different regions
- Link with OGs
- Building a decentralized IT system

3) Expectations from the workshop

The workshop will be a success for the participants if:

- Requirements and ideas for partial implementation are provided for a common TN platform: how to maintain a virtual network for exchange and TN mutual coaching, how to create a High Impact Knowledge Reservoir (HIKR) based on the MAA
- Own TN can be expanded, a better cooperation between the TNs, better modularity and interoperability between the TNs
- Lots of input from participants to project partners are given
- Feedback is given on the impact of my TN
- Recommendations for future TNs are filed based on TN success stories, sharing of experiences (strengths & weaknesses of TNs and how to improve them), views and concepts; demonstration of interesting and useful TNs and new approaches
- A clear view is obtained on the MA processes, who the involved actors are in TNs, what types of TN outputs are produced, and who the targeted end users for TN-outputs are; get new information about TNs (objectives, materials); recognize different aspects & experiences for efficient TN management; insights about TN functioning and practices
- The view of farmers and advisors becomes clearer; building on the experience of end-user groups that are present here

- The needs of the present TNs are understood and the project can find ways help; learn from EURAKNOS and from each other
- New contacts are made, networking is happening, and connections are made to people working in the same field
- Interaction between Rural Networks & innovation implementation is improved
- If participants feel empowered, believe TNs to be strong & successful tool towards a sustainable Agriculture / Forestry

4) TN top priorities

TN top priorities defined by the participants could be categorized in four main categories: digital, knowledge, collaboration, communication and dissemination

Digital

- A portal for common storage and to showcase problems and solutions
- A forum or a chat which allows interaction between different actors e.g. a place where farmers can ask for help/questions
- Built on existing platforms like Facebook or something like Olivipedia, Reddit or Instagram
- All output should be easily retrievable via a robust search engine
- An ideal TN should function as an app for daily use
- It should provide digital support structures that allow to share problems, expertise, solutions and that can bring actors together. In addition, the digital platform should provide a clear overview of all TNs and allow to profile users and only present content that is fit to their level of expertise and in their preferred language (automatic profiling and translation). Also, the platform should use user analytics to further optimize this + evaluations and feedback forms on the solutions and outputs it generates. This would allow the TN to improve them and adapt them, so they stay relevant (see the iterative spiral from the ‘Community of Practice’)

Knowledge/Content

- It needs to be practical expertise that can inspire farmers to apply and innovate (field-based)
- The ideal TN should also target ‘analogue users’ and increase the digital literacy of their end users via training and considering the innovation adaptation curve
- The ideal TN should have clear targets and narrow focus on the problem it wants to solve, within a certain sector by knowing (needs, problems, preferences & barriers) of end users, in particular farmers, through involving these from the start. This could be done by linking with existing or by starting new OGs to do this via a bottom-up approach
- Resources and (financial) incentives to engage end users are needed and to connect local OGs across Members States in a peer-to-peer fashion
- Farmers and advisors are also knowledge providers, therefore we need a 2-way knowledge exchange
- It should tackle technological, economic and ecological problems of the 21st century
- It should be kept alive and updated; the ideal TN should be sustainable and ensure that the project results stay available for the intended target audiences and beyond, even after the project has ended
- It should be embedded in the everyday market
- It should be edited by advisor-experts, translated into practical knowledge, provided in tailored formats, specific to user profiles

Collaboration

- There should be a common interest in innovation by all actors
- The TN should have a flexible, dynamic, roadmap on the solutions it wants to develop and co-create this with the best experts, different actors that are required to solve the problem. Participants should be able

to change their role during the project lifetime. End users (e.g. noble farmers) should be involved in this process to ensure the user friendliness and the feasibility of the solutions that are being developed.

- Everybody should have a clear view on the process, the intermediate steps and their role within the process. This should be translated in some sort of TN ‘Code of Conduct’ to clearly spell out expectations and roles. Moreover, additional resources should also be spent to create a culture of trust within a TN via team building to enforce the ‘Code of Conduct’. There should be governance goals and drive
- It should focus on co-creation, co-creation of knowledge should be facilitated by a diverse community although there is a need for ‘expert facilitators’ to facilitate the collaboration between all actors and smoothen the process
- It should build and grow an interactive ‘Community of Practice’ that can refine the solutions and enhance the uptake in an iterative learning spiral by creating regional pilots and by A/B testing in different regions to consider regional differences
- TNs should cover all regions and countries worldwide. There should be as many partners/participants as there are Member States, moreover it should clearly state at what level it was made, ideally the TN should have a multi-layered structure in the network considering the local, regional, national and EU level from start to end, there also should be an EU TN defined by local groups and dynamic links at the national/EU-level with regular meetings
- It should allow actors to stay connected e.g. it should help reconnect people to the food-chain, together with consumers; we should talk about all actors as ‘partners’
- It shouldn’t be about end users only, but about partners active in the consortium
- It should be a comfortable cooperation, with active participation of all partners, fostering personal relations, and group meetings. TNs should have ‘trust building’ phase with partners, but also towards end users who need to get to know and trust a TN. TNs should have more time, people and financing

Communication & dissemination

- C&D should be via tailored channels adapted to user profile and to specific sharing goals: e.g. videos of the best cases with co-created content; local meetings and conferences should be used; web TV should be set up to approach potential younger targets, there should be cross-visits of different actors; meetings with farmers to exchange ideas and showcases
- Training and support should be provided by the TN
- The content should be adapted to the MS and region
- There should be clear targets and no buzz words, written in the farmer’s native language (no language barriers, translation should be provided)
- TNs should receive help from the government; here is a crucial role for NRNs to act as multipliers (local outreach)
- A lot of budget should be spent on actual dissemination, even in a separate project after the project has ended.
- TNs should have more time to compile the knowledge and disseminate materials in an efficient way
- An ideal TN should provide a toolbox that facilitates peer 2 peer sharing among farmers

5) Impact of communication and dissemination

Participants had the reflections on how TNs can (better) reach the target audience and how to improve the TN website, the use of social media, in particular Twitter and LinkedIn, and YouTube.

Reaching the target audience

Reaching at least 60% of the target audience means that you have identified and listed all end users and kept track of all communication efforts/impacts (direct & indirect). Most of the participants don’t know if a TN can reach or has reached the majority of their target audiences through communication, and in particular dissemination activities. One of the main reasons is because lack of the time for strategic communication, to explain all aspects,

and to organise information that needs to be communicated. TNs emphasise informal knowledge exchange which is difficult to measure but important for the sustainability of the TN. Some topics do not allow to measure this as potential end-users also include young people who could become farmers.

Do we know enough about the end users? And is it possible to adapt our communication and dissemination?

In some cases, the target for C & D was never clearly defined and therefore not measured. Particularly, uptake of results and the measurement of indirect impact. How to distinguish the project's influence from others? Often there is not enough time and resources to do this properly, since the most results are only disseminated at the end of the project's lifetime. 'Hard-to-reach' profiles are more difficult. Sometimes there is no trust, nor an immediate benefit that can be demonstrated, which negatively impacts the uptake of results. Often the focus is on advisors but farmers are also an important target group. A classical way to measure impact is google analytics, but this is not a guarantee for impact as analytics do not differentiate between persistency of engagers and usual audience and the profile of the visitors or followers is not clear. Social media and measuring systems (SEO) don't allow to define the occupation as this depends on the user's decision to give insight so it's impossible to define the exact audience. Quantitative indicator such as the number of participants with online materials, number of registrants in database, or the number of downloads or views of certain output material does not always present the real situation. For example, the number of participants at events only represent the people who are present and not always the number of persons that we have reached. Lots of people simply don't have time to participate. Some users have no broadband connection or lack digital skills. Some users are not interested.

Some TNs, such as 4D4E, measured it with user analytics in a learning community, but this created additional barriers, e.g. the need for registration. AgriDemo-F2F¹⁹ did try to analyse impact by doing telephone interviews 6 months after the demos, but the results are currently being processed.

The reason they were successful is because the activities were always targeted to a specific end user group with a narrow focus and adapted to their needs (local language, easy to understand). You need to set a clear target and needs should be region specific; interaction with key players is crucial, this demands lots of 'legwork' by a facilitator. There is a better chance to success and impact if TN partners have a broad reach and connections, existing partner channels and networks can be very useful. Also, a connection to existing OGs, end user groups and other networks at national and local level is contributing to the level of dissemination, uptake of results and hence the level of success of a TN. Also, the use of professional teachers or a known and trusted education platform can be an added value.

Some end users will remain very difficult to reach: all farmers only interact and take up materials they trust or via people or channels they trust. This is especially true for the 'harder to reach' profiles (profile 1, see ANNEX III). So, TNs need to create a community or leverage existing communities. Moreover, using existing channels, network organizations, farmers' networks, or relevant and known news outlets and media contacts, instead of reinventing the wheel is crucial. A mapping of relevant resources and contacts for TNs can be very interesting. TNs often naturally have a very specific focus on those that are willing to hear the message and those you can reach and use them as influencers to get a multiplication effect (go from easy to 'harder to reach user' profile according to the innovation adaptation curve). For example, in Belgium and the Netherlands only 2% of the farmers can be considered as innovators. In general, most projects take this innovation adoption curve into account and they first target and work with the farmers that are open for innovation (profile 3) and then they 'hope' that they will convince the early adopters (profile 2, see ANNEX III), who should convince the early and late majority (profile 1, see ANNEX III). However, a clear strategy with support tools to leverage this knowledge transfer effect is almost never in place.

Extensive targeted and systemic market investigation before the project is in the main stage a good way to ensure impact. Innovative technology product offered as solution to a real problem on the field and increasing market competitiveness for the farmer has more chance to create impact. Direct contact with a large number of farmers, including feedback, is a measure that can increase impact. However, one had to consider that face to face meetings are often claimed as best ways to disseminate but often the same people, in case farmers, turn up, so that is a peer

¹⁹ <https://agridemo-h2020.eu/>

bias. Traditional farmers are not really open to new technologies which are communicated by experts from EU projects. It is also difficult to identify newcomers and successors. The continuation of projects and interlinking to other projects and networks is also important. Language is also a critical factor in dissemination and hence the uptake of results.

It is difficult to know the size of the target audience that has been reached or the number of implementations. Measuring outreach doesn't equate to generating impact. Moreover, broad reach is not obvious because often TNs have no direct connection with the farmers and there is a lot of competition in information channels for farmers. Therefore, the linkage of TNs to existing networks and end user groups is crucial. There is a lack of knowledge and tools on how to measure outreach or response rates, as well as a lack of time and budget to measure the outreach. Measuring the outreach might not be conceptually possible in some cases and some potentially targeted end users will remain very difficult to reach and get hold on. A thorough pre-project market investigation and farmers consultation can contribute to the success of the project and the impact of the dissemination in terms of uptake of results. Sometimes there is no trust or an immediate benefit that can be demonstrated which negatively impacts the uptake of results. Additionally, it is not always confirmed that effective outreach is actually a parameter sufficiently considered by funding agencies, lack of time and budget is often the main cause of not or not sufficient evaluating the impact of dissemination activities (such as feedback with farmers/foresters and/or advisors).

Website, Social Media (Twitter, LinkedIn) & YouTube

Website

- The front (home) page should be simple (e.g. sidebar often too complex)
- Rethink information architecture: time that is needed to find the information the end user is a limiting factor especially for farmers
- Make a dynamic website (not static); suggestion: directional profile, add blogs and ask questions; more engagement of end users with content
- Use photos and videos, also add visual material to the home page (e.g. short video)
- Link to social media
- Add graphs to convince practitioners
- Headlines for an easier reading experience
- Avoid too much text, short and clear messages
- Use easy wordings (do not use jargon)
- Translate in different languages
- The presented content on the website should address also primary producers be adapted to the needs of the different end user groups in terms of language and engaging content; don't focus too much on the project itself but on the results of the project, output oriented content
- Clear choices need to be made regarding the websites and platforms to reach relevant end users with easy identifiable and application-oriented content
- These communication tools can allow more interaction with the end users by asking questions and gaining feedback
- All messages need to be relevant to the point and instantly provide value. Therefore, the content should also be easily searchable and findable, e.g. via keywords (high signal to noise ratio within a max of 5 clicks).
- In terms of the format, the less text and the more visual and interactive the better. The actual content needs to be adapted to the local conditions (language) and to local farmers (expertise level), as much as possible. This makes the content more authentic and creates trust.

Twitter:

Twitter is not the right channel for farmers (only in some countries e.g. UK)

- TNs' posts on Twitter are in English, this is a language barrier; moreover, social media language can be very difficult to adapt to the user
- There is no trigger for end users, it seems more directed to officials, policy makers, other TNs and the EIP-AGRI community as such
- Adding 'key' hashtags may be useful such as #TN #Explanation #Farmer

LinkedIn:

- Not all farmers are in LinkedIn
- Posts are in English, this is a restriction
- Use flags instead of written text to communicate which languages are available
- Facebook is better
- When linking to another website it should be clear what it is about
- Add polls to content to make it more engaging
- Link the post through an influencing person with social media
- Articles should be the message not e.g. the newsletter as such
- Don't use too many tags, when using tags be specific, tags should highlight the problem/solution

YouTube: Video

- Context should be clear
- Content should be adapted to end user e.g. demos on the field; problem solution oriented
- Clear communication
- Chose the right communicator, person with a broad network, influential, good speaker

6) Content and selection criteria

Ways of farmers/foresters to communicate their needs to the TN

- The first strategy is to involve end users in the partnership of the consortium. This implies that they should already be actively involved in the proposal writing phase when the project concept and methodology are conceived
- The second strategy is to organize participatory workshops, meetings, or scoping seminars with end users at the start of the project and during the projects. This can be best done by involving local networks, like operational groups, multipliers (farm extension services or cooperatives) or by setting up regional nodes as local hubs to meet TN partners and share needs, information and potential solutions, with key influencers; reflections should be made after all meetings
- The third strategy is to organize F2F interviews or perform a large-scale surveys and questionnaires through existing networks or channels, e.g. existing farmer consulting systems; these can however be unreliable as there can be a sampling bias
- One final innovative storytelling strategy was used by the TN Agrispin²⁰ ([Deliverable 1.5](#)). They started by asking all partners of the consortium to write a story about a farm innovation that they were working on, their role, the journey they had taken so far and the lessons they had learned in their own words. Next, they also collected the dreams of participants during F2F workshops
- Through intermediaries such as farmer organisations, local network representatives, yearly national steering group meetings
- At stakeholder events, such as study days, fairs, innovation audit by an innovation broker etc.
- They have to be contacted by a TN, they won't proactively communicate their needs e.g. during farm visits, through direct dialogue
- Interviews for evaluation (post monitoring) and next steps is key; learnings: 'What didn't work?', 'What did work': need to test different formats from one-to-one, one-to-many, one-to-all, many-to-many, many-to-all, all-to-all.

²⁰ <https://agrispin.eu/>

There is a need for a reflective exercise across the TN as to what is a good way to detect farmers' needs. For instance, when a farmer becomes a member of an organisation, their characteristics could be asked and interesting information can be acquired. At regional meetings specific knowledge gaps can be identified. The participants suggested a need to use multiple channels in order to gain more knowledge about the farmers needs. There are several strategies that a TN can use to better elucidate end user (farmer/forester) needs and to build trust among end users.

Criteria for usefulness of TN outputs for a common platform or e-KRP

- It should not be a 'network-based' KR, but a 'content based' KR
- There should be a region of interest and a potential for replicability across areas
- Only relevant information and results that give real solutions to real needs and problems, user oriented specific content that can make a difference and create impact
- Only proven (used) best practices (this should be a separate category, number of downloads can be an indication of interest and validity)
- Conditions should be described in which the innovation works well, now it is often the technology and not the context that is given
- Learnings: "What did work?" and "What did not work?", ranking by end users
- OG requirements could be a checklist
- Show 'failures might seem an idea, but this could lead to commercial legislation and/or legal disputes
- As long that there is online space available, there is no particular need for selectivity
- Innovation is time bound, some ideas might not be popular now, but they might become popular a bit later
- Results should be differentiated between general and country specific, all should be available, maybe in a short form
- Regardless of the usefulness of the knowledge, the importance lies in the sharing of the knowledge, leaders (e.g. TN coordinators) will validate it
- All output is useful to some extent, different criteria should apply to different products/outputs
- Clear labelling is crucial, e.g. is the output a practice abstract, a case study or an opinion piece
- Different formats needed, different versions of content (e.g. short/long/audio/video)
- There's a need for a clear framework for the interpretation of the output
- Farmers should be able to react to output, classified y potential use, for farmers or other TNs
- Project related information should only be on the TN website (technical info)

If the knowledge base is too selective, interesting and innovative knowledge could be lost because it doesn't meet certain predefined criteria. If the knowledge base is not selective, then it needs to be very clear how specific output should be interpreted by means of clear labelling. There is also a risk that farmers might not want to share all relevant data on being innovative.

Level of expertise required to create and curate content (what is needed and who should do it)

- Content should be created/collected by the MA approach led by the consortium, the TN as such is responsible
- Funding bodies should also evaluate the content
- Internal evaluation should be done by the consortium and actors, user validation should be part of this process or 'on top' after the validation by the consortium
- To curate one needs to know the audience for whom the content is meant
- One needs to have subject knowledge and communication skills to be able to write/reproduce the outputs/results in a comprehensive way
- Describing the context, condition in which the innovation works is key

- It needs to be as open as possible;
- There is a need for clear labels, is this scientific content or rather a radical idea;
- There's a need for a validation process, which needs to be well defined at the beginning;
- Only a few people can validate, which demands a lot of effort from these people and causes it to fail in the end as not all the partners in the project don't care about the validation; it can also be inefficient if validation has to be done by too many people;
- There is a need to define a clear governance structure at the onset of the project;
- It is important to ask where the TN info/knowledge/outputs will eventually end up;
- A mixed system such as Wikipedia is interesting because it allows the users to see the history of specific output, but it could also allow the user to signal that output is outdated and needs to be re-evaluated. But people will have to want this and get recognition for their efforts;
- There is a need for best practices on how to curate content;
- There is no need to be selective, as long as very good filters are in place. Moreover, it is very difficult use certain criteria, since specific TN outputs may be only relevant to some people and not to others. To decide on this in advance is very difficult. Therefore, filters are needed, such as A) a good categorization with keywords (geography, sectors, themes, needs, expertise, solutions, content type, origin, date, etc.) when you want to browse and be inspired or B) a very good and narrow search function (like google) when you want to find specifically what you are looking for;
- The FarmDemo²¹ hub that was set up by AgriDemo-F2F, PLAID²² and Nefertiti²³ uses questions, instead of keywords or categories to guide the users to the results that are most relevant for them;
- Additional search options or evaluation systems to better filter the content on the e-KRP could be very useful, such as user analytics, user reviews of content, content suggestions (e.g. Amazon function: user that were interested in this were also interested in these alternatives) or a 'bot' that helps you to the information you need by an interactive virtual conversation (Q&A);
- To decide on the input, the filters and categorization of the content when it is first stored in the e-KRP, the partners or TNs that were involved in creating the content should be involved as much as possible, since they know best which categories and filters apply;
- To help curate the content, the managers of the platform best decide based on user analytics and user feedback;
- The TN coordinator and Management Board could also play an important role here.

Setting up a process to curate and validate TN outputs may one hand create the feeling that one is protected against inferior output quality, but this process is likely to fail, so it is better to clearly label output, which still requires a lot of time and effort. Regardless of whether this is determined in a democratic or dictatorial way, this needs to be clearly defined at the start and be done in a transparent manner.

Transforming knowledge and data in a standardised TN/e-KRP format (who)

- The database (or e-KRP) should have standardised formats;
- If the transformation of knowledge is done by a centralised unit, value can get lost;
- There's a need for a degree of standardisation going from tailor-made solutions to highly standardised content depending on who the output is for;
- It depends on what will be transformed the e.g. format or the text;
- There is also a way to standardise by theme or by country to better fit the needs of the end users;
- Standardisation can happen of the front-end and/or the back-end, this can have an impact on the user-friendliness;

²¹ <https://farmdemo.eu/>

²² <https://plaid-h2020.hutton.ac.uk/>

²³ <https://nefertiti-h2020.eu/>

- To determine data standards for the e-KRP should best be done in collaboration with the EIP-AGRI

Only when it is clear how output needs to be standardised and what exactly will be standardised, it can be determined who is able to do it.

7) Engaging in the multi-actor approach (MAA)

Potential actors and end users of the TN MAA

The type of actors that are important for a good MAA and that can also be considered as potential end users are

- Focus should be more on the practitioners, farmers
- Value chain (traders, processors, retailers, consumers...) in particular industrial suppliers (feed, seed, fertiliser, agrochemicals, machinery etc.)
- Consumers: to educate them about agriculture
- Administration: as they often form an important threshold
- Policy makers at EU national, regional, local & regulatory authorities
- Media: to communicate the importance of agriculture
- Researchers
- Students: as potential farmers and foresters
- Teachers/educators
- Young entrepreneurs
- Farmers associations
- Networks or groups of farmers such as OGs, cooperatives
- National Rural Networks
- Ecotourism: as branding (vacation at a farm) and a different business model
- NGOs/Activists: in order to prevent potential thresholds and co-create possible solutions
- Capital providers
- Professionals: to provide expert knowledge often lacking in TNs

It is the TN's role to decide on the type of actors who should be involved. It is important for the TN to stay independent. Including a professional communication agency or professional journalist is an asset.

MAA Bottlenecks of TNs

- Understanding each other (communicating science to farmers)
- Budget, more actors means more expenses, it's hard to have an oversight of costs (
- Alignment towards the same goal
- Digital communication/reliability
- Timing of activities, difficult to reach farmers during harvesting time or students during summer
- Time from actors
- Engaging actors; proper incentives for each actor, especially end users and actors outside the partner countries of a TN
- Farmers have sometimes rigid minds, they don't want to change things that have always been done in that way
- How to express the voice of each actor
- How to avoid friction between competitors
- Stakeholder fatigue
- Need for experienced facilitators
- Need for open minded actors
- Different levels of dedication

- Different languages
- Different needs for each actor
- How to engage other farmers than “privileged farmers” (usual suspects)

Availability, the alignment of the different actors towards the same goals and understanding each other are perceived as the top three difficulties to tackle in order to achieve a better the MAA.

Ways to overcome MAA bottlenecks

According to the participants possible solutions to overcome the difficulties that can be experienced in TNs are the following:

- Use an award for alignment, NEWBIE²⁴ has a ‘newbie award’ for actors in the network. Every partner country gives a yearly award: the actors have to agree on the best criteria for the best business model, so they’ll need to discuss the goal.
- Train facilitation skills for all actors, by making a facilitator part of the consortium (soft skills): to bring all actors together and make them work together, everybody needs to remain engaged and seen, and contribute.
- Facilitation networks to solve common problems and educate facilitation.
- Make A common time schedule for all actors: to be able to gather them all; they could e.g. meet at a farm.
- Make actors’ agreements from the beginning; clear vision on activities; participation in decision process at conceptualisation, initiation and execution phase. One-on-one conversations are necessary with the main coordinator to start building trust. For the whole project to go well and no one would feel left out/used/run over.
- Identify best methodologies for MAAs handbook with practical examples for coordinators, partners and team facilitators. This should be based on actual practices and validated regularly in order to achieve a common understanding of the approach, better organisation of project activities, and being effective in implementing the MAA.
- Involve the right actors-partners. A good preliminary analysis of the subject and potential partners/actors based on previous experience and trust. The right actors are crucial for the success of the project.
- Get specialised non-agricultural partners (e.g. facilitators) involved from the start. TNs need to have the right people in the right place. Including one main expert with facilitation skills per country who is very willing to do this. Facilitators should provide 1-week training for the well-functioning and success of the TN and set up inspiration and evaluation meetings (e.g. 1 per year). This will help to keep actors engaged and to support the MAA, build and repair trust within a TN, to determine the actors and set goals and expectations and create a clear vision, to capture TN activities/issues and solve them, to prevent road-blocks and keep the network energised and functioning as well as working together, to keep innovation trials on trade methodology of innovation development (innovation spiral).
- Stimulate actors’ engagement by showing casing them simple solutions to real life problems like organising practical visits to real farms to see problems they had and how they solved it. This will solve the lack of interest and imagination of certain actors to be able to respond to end users’ needs and problems on the field.
- Define needs and connect users to their engagement, by defining and clustering needs (across regions, but keep aligning point). This will increase engagement & improve project results, impact and sustainability.
- Thinking of potential benefits for each actor such as money, showcase, publicity, teaching material, knowledge. This depends on the type of actor and it will increase motivation.
- The coordinators and partners have to be honest about the budget and ask other TNs how much they spend on what, what they’ve learned from previous mistakes, and assume that everything has a cost (such

²⁴ <http://www.newbie-academy.eu/>

- as monitoring & education). This will create long-term sustainability, have a higher impact and better implementation.
- Prioritise activities by the actors to solve the issue of lack of time.
 - Timing of the engagement with a calendar and clock. Consider availability as a function of the cycle of nature (respect nature, respect farmers), create a common calendar. Respect the local habits with regard to timing (event start and end around lunchtime).
 - Enhance farmer's participation through making use of intermediaries and using social research methodology and mapping the flow of information. This will increase impact.
 - Regular feedback loops on WPs of all actors by organising meetings and activities (with the whole network not only for facilitators and practitioners). This should strengthen the awareness of the process and one's role in the process.
 - Stimulate networking between actors by doing visits together and allow time for networking as well as a devoted social media presence in order make them feel like more of a community.
 - Story telling by collecting stories, stimulate people to write them down (moderation) to illustrate what processes are all about and how they could intervene.
 - Incentive4balance: events (field visits, meetings, boot camps) where actors present problems and receive solutions from peers. Creating a farming Hackathon this would balance the giving and taking.
 - Increase the time and budget of TNs and OGs. Time is money, and this would allow better organisation.
 - Find multiplier actors and appropriate national/regional networks.
 - Relay findings and knowledge from TN to target group and engage outside TNs and countries
 - Engage and express all voices from outside (real farm context), by using different methods, and providing equal opportunity to be heard (create the right setting)
 - Engage outside countries and partners by having a set proportion and budget that can be allocated in the first year of the project to extent the impact geographically and technically.
 - Allocate the right budget for events, provide enough budget for travelling and translation in order to allow foreign actors to attend international events.
 - Hunt for open-mindedness by mapping the needs of farmers, advisors, policy makers and researchers, and teaming them up so as to help them develop skills they do not possess adequately. Why: To find open-minded actors to promote sustainable innovation.
 - Provide training and coaching in order to connect by creating a trainers' pool, organising trainings in different countries, creating a network and create actions towards enabling community in order to increase awareness about MA processes and to provide tools to steer energy.
 - Search for innovators, finding open-minded actors by asking other partners. Why: Because they are the ones that have the innovations to be shared.
 - Find early adopters, how to involve farmers by calling them, asking for recommendations and networking to identify best practices to share (peer learning).
 - Involve farmers from the beginning of the project as a partner by finding them during the partnership setting-up to save budget, time and increase engagement
 - Incentivise farmers by providing the possibility to pay for their time and ending replacement labour to encourage farmers to disseminate their innovation where they do not lose the commercial benefit.
 - Organise a flexible process by defining groups of actors, organising good formats and installing reflection moments as such less attention needs to go to the process itself.

Many problems that are being experienced in the TN MAA can be overcome by making use of an experienced facilitator, selecting a person who is able to have both perspectives, the research and the practice, who shows empathy, talks appropriately to different actors and has already created a network. The correct person in the correct place can make a huge difference.

8) The ideal TN

Different scenarios were made by 9 groups of participants for an ideal TN. The different scenario's set out what each TN can do individually and what can be outsourced to a common platform or system. Each presentation on the 9 ideal TNs were recorded and can be found each You Tube link respectively.

SCENARIO 1 <https://youtu.be/s5VJ0wDrfKM>

- From a TN will define and choose the topic and define the actors to involve. We will manage that by involving people and being dynamic. That is what we keep in term of the MAA. The content creation and how we tailor it will be done during the lifetime of the TN by the consortium. In terms of C&D: webpage, newsletters, meetings, seminars, workshops and social media will be organized with the actors of the TN. Knowledge will be stored in a common KR, a platform where it is possible to find practical solutions. This should be done in a collaborative way. We need to be able to define metadata and tag the content that we want to put online. This needs to be easy and friendly to use, without many barriers and with a list of contacts so people can identify who provided the content. In addition, the possibility to have feedback reports on how to use the KR should be developed. Content alerts will be included, which means that every time there is something new the community should be informed about it, should be included. It should be possible to measure or reflect end-user and TN community satisfaction. Contents should be translated by the central system, e.g. documents, in all MS languages. Useful templates and guidelines should be foreseen for TNs on how to best perform the MAA and, guidelines on how to best use social media, social science methodologies, social science resources and social science experts, so the TNs can improve the engagement of the actors. Identify all the media channels and contacts in terms of TN communication in a media list.

SCENARIO 2 HABIT.ACT <https://youtu.be/SydBwtAkySU>

- The main goal of our future TN, Habit.Act, is to change the habits of all actors, i.e. consumers and farmers, in order to have an impact on climate change. We will focus on mixed farming systems and we will work with different actors involved in order to share experiences. For the MAA we focus on free local clusters to avoid language barriers, in 3 countries, where we have one cluster each. There is a coordinator in each cluster: a social scientist, both as a coordinator of the project and as a facilitator, because we want to have someone that can make a good connection between the different actors. Then we involve farmers, consumers, NGOs, trainers, policy makers and journalists to disseminate to the public in the local language. English will only be used for general consortium meetings and for the policy brief aka dissemination to policy makers. Knowledge will be adapted for different end users. We will create specific knowledge for farmers about the mixed farming system, for consumers about the farm in general, for researchers, etc. We will use standardised templates and guidelines in order to have a continuation and not reinvent the wheel. Local languages and English will be used for dissemination. For the e-platform, we aim to share experiences by recording activities so everybody can have a look on what is going on at a farm. We also want to create e-learning for students and farm games for children to learn how a farm is functioning. We also want to connect peers with the creation of "Farminder" (like Tinder) and a chat feature to ensure that consumers and farmers can exchange problems, solutions and ways of working together. In terms of C & D, we will use EURAKNOS as a channel, so to boost our reach via the social media of EURAKNOS, its newsletter and the policy connection. However, we want to have the added value solutions implemented locally, as opposed to EURAKNOS, which is more implemented as a network at international level. We also want to organize cross visits between different local clusters and demonstration days for consumers. Farmers will be encouraged to spend some days in other farms abroad as an exchange programme with a farm holiday agency as a business model. We also want to involve consumers that they can directly invest in farmers that are producing locally.

SCENARIO 3 THE FUTURE FOR BEEF <https://youtu.be/qWGRQHbrXqU>

- In the TN "Future for Beef" we will develop a tool to reduce carbon emissions and to increase feed conversion efficiency, called Verify Emissions, Gasses and Nutrition aka "VEGAN". We will involve a variety of actors aka 'Beef Stakeholders', such as end users, farm organization, applied universities, (beef) industries, specialists in C&D. We will also have a steering group and advisory board. We will organize two

kick off meetings, one for stakeholders, one for the involved farmers. We will align them in the project and make sure that everyone is going in the same direction and to meet project deadlines. After two years, we will organize an international symposium where we will present results and together with other relevant TNs and OG. Related to content: we start with a consumer survey, after that we will develop C&D project videos to show our progress, including a state-of-the-art forum with state-of-the-art research. After that we will proceed with the tool development, best practice guides and links to OGs in Europe to develop the tool in Europe. We will also organize a best-practice award across Europe in 28 countries. We will create a Knowledge Reservoir to create content and pass it on to EURAKNOS that can disseminate it further. We will use a social media community reservoir. EURAKNOS can also help us link to OGs and provide templates for C&D so we can adapt them for our own project and make our results more visible. EURAKNOS can also provide a ‘white label’ platform that we can use and customize it to promote our own results and data during the project. Afterwards this can be integrated with the results of other projects in a centralized database. Build our own website. To make sure it is sustainable, we can build a business model and ensure farmers can use it in the future, make it “future proof” and make sure that the platform is implemented by the farmers themselves. Have connection between partners and local products where there is beef production. Start with a core group of partners, but then add partners during the lifetime of the TN. Common templates and services will be used, such as data management and storage, templates for C & D, etc.

SCENARIO 4: <https://youtu.be/HVtOBsopE30>

- Our TN wants to collaborate with EURAKNOS as a generalized international entity or standard, but wants to keep its own identity. Therefore, we want to keep control of the formation of the consortium, the MAA to be invited, the type of knowledge collected in the TN, the shared vision of the TN. However, there is added value of working with a huge, centralized Knowledge Repository. We want to provide knowledge and data to a common platform, but it should not be a simple duplication of content (copy from website). It should add more value and create an experience to do something as a designated destination. For example, with different learning modules based on the TN knowledge library, such as on pig farming, arable farming or organic farming. So, to provide custom courses based on the knowledge libraries from the TNs, where farmers or other end users could learn and even get certificates. It could also add an interactive forum for peer-to-peer learning and provide coaching services for how to engage the next generation of farmers and have them interact with older generations. Besides fora for end users, a forum for TNs to foster peer-to-peer learning would also be interesting to support the next generation of TNs. EURAKNOS should build the back-end and functionality of this platform. All services should be free for the first 3 years during the life of the TN and the value should be established by the TNs and involved farmer organisations. Afterwards different business models and subscription services for those farmer associations could be explored to keep the content up-to-date and demonstrate the added value in the future. Normally dissemination peaks after content creation at the end of the TN, but thanks to EURAKNOS this level might decrease later or even increase.

SCENARIO 5 <https://youtu.be/j6afCyae5W8>

- TNs will last more than the established years, e.g. one extra year to maintain the Knowledge Reservoir and to check the impact of the TN. To do this interviews and surveys could be done to check if farmers actually implemented new business models and solutions. We will also check what farmers really want and provide them with easy and understandable videos and materials with advice. We will organize farm demonstration and networking days to connect farmers, especially young farmers that are implementing new technologies. We will also give networking tips to connect with other farmers. We expect that EURAKNOS will give us some templates on what materials work and what not and a toolbox to look to specific information. We will promote a contest between young farmers to implement innovative ideas. We will use different adapted channels and moving labs on how the actual situation on the farm is. Finally, we will also create a platform to help farmers to have better equipment by exchanging and renting it out.

SCENARIO 6 <https://youtu.be/gVQVvPYxVOA>

- We want to tackle two things that are quite contrary: having EURAKNOS saying “we know everything about TNs” and at the same time be very specific based on the users and selection criteria that is needed. How to approach this more systematically? Provide some agreed and obligatory first level of the repository. In this way, it is easier to overcome the language barrier. And give the versatility and specifics to TN leaders to communicate. Having responsible players in each step of the system. The future TN is the network that receives the benefit of EURAKNOS, they will set and make use of the strategy by using resources of someone else. Let general public of users of EURAKNOS repository to make their vision of the business plan. In the end everybody should be searching on EURAKNOS. Having something like google (simple in interface, but all knowing). Push notifications, based in certain criteria, could also be developed.

SCENARIO 7 <https://youtu.be/RITvDOs7ay0>

- Looking to a future TN after EURAKNOS has been setup in 5 years. The content will be unchanged because EURAKNOS will always be at EU scale. The networks have to be always local and national. This is something the consortium will do themselves. EURAKNOS will help to standardize the content that is created by TNs by developing designated tools + explanation on how to use the tools to ensure consistent dissemination. EURAKNOS should continue the network after the project. This should ideally be user specific and dynamic. It is essential to specify where the TN will go after the end of the project. Create a website that merges all the websites of TNs, so visitors of one TN will also visit the websites of other TNs and get the bigger picture. And having an umbrella system will be easier to find actors in other projects, like social scientists or designers, or types of training, that will be supervised by an administrator (TN coordinator). EURAKNOS could help in the sustainability of the TN.

SCENARIO 8 <https://youtu.be/eLlVlKs9tw>

- Our TN is called ‘Food for future generation’. The project starts with a core group who really carry the ideas. We will start with a basket of questions (no answers). Next, we need to find allies and EURAKNOS can help with this. So, people that really like the idea of joining the TN from different stakeholders’ groups, like farmers consumers, retailers, schools, local governments, researchers etc. This is what we call the warm network of people that share an ambition to find solutions, not representatives. Next, we need to formulate a proposal involving the cold network that have to open possibilities, like managers and representatives. They have their own interests and targets and they can add their own questions to the basket to feed in the proposal to submit to Brussels. We need to keep all these actors involved before the approval and implementation of the project proposal. The main thing in the proposal is that you need to include space to explore and to grow and discover. It is important to brainstorm with young generation and analyses data statistics, find the right expertise, etc. Build a network that can sustain after the project period to ensure sustainability and to keep fuelling the movement. Moreover, it is important to keep the cold network online.

SCENARIO 9 <https://youtu.be/v9BLZngPLJE>

- EURAKNOS can provide technical support, such as contacts to experts, like IT specialists for technical support. EURAKNOS can also provide the right contacts, collecting all regional advisors contacts and facilitators. That way TNs can build on each other’s networks. The same advisor can cover different networks and gain more expertise. Co-creation of knowledge by using key existing partners. Use the database of EURAKNOS to know what exists about technical information (so we can prioritize as a new TN) and communication channels that work very well. In this way, we don’t have to redo things that actually already exist. This will help save time. TNs can also include new business models after the project is done.

4. Conclusions

TNs are dealing with pressing needs in agriculture and forestry to meet current challenges in agricultural innovation. WP2 is dealing with the compilation and evaluation of existing TNs (28). The participatory workshop in Budapest (11-13 September 2020) gathered 58 different actors, (26 EURAKNOS and 32 KIP members), amongst

which EURAKNOS end users (TNs) and TN outputs end users (advisors, farmers and foresters). During the workshop, the results of WP2 achieved so far were discussed and validated as input for WP3.

Based on the outcomes of the discussions of the WP2 results (Task 2.1, 2.2, 2.3 and 2.4), the sharing of ideas and experiences on best TN practices and methodologies in the view of making a common shared TN platform with a standardised and harmonised approach, 20 conclusions were drawn in the form of recommendations. These recommendations relate to the main different aspects of TNs: content, content storage, C&D and the MAA.

The recommendations are listed below in process order, starting with the conceptualisation and initiation phase of a TN project up until the finalisation.

Colour coded links are made in relation to the four main aspects of TNs that are investigated in WP2 (see below). Where possible some case examples of TNs are also given to illustrate the recommendations.

[TN content](#) (creation of outputs)

[TN content storage](#) (how outputs are stored)

[TN C&D](#) (uptake and promotion of outputs)

[TN MAA](#) (who involved and how)

1. TN Purpose:

The TN should have a **clear and narrow focus** on the problem it wants to solve within a certain sector **by** asking end users the right questions in order to **understand and address the needs, problems, preferences & barriers of end users. For TNs to address end users' needs it is imperative they are involved from the conceptualisation phase.** In the true spirit of co-creation and the co-innovation model in Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS), **the TN ceases to talk about end users**, but will consider all involved actors as partners or knowledge producers who can mutually learn from each other ([TN content](#) + [TN MAA](#) + [TN C&D](#)).

This bottom-up approach that a TN can use to better elucidate end-user (farmer/forester/advisor) needs, is vital to **build trust** with and between them **in the initiation phase**. There are several strategies for doing this (these different strategies are best combined):

- A. The first strategy is to **involve 'end users' in the partnership of the consortium**. This implies that they should already be actively involved in the proposal-writing phase when the project concept and methodology are conceived.
- B. The second strategy is to **organize workshops or scoping seminars with 'end users'** at the start of the project. This can be best done by involving local networks, linking with existing operational groups (OGs) or starting new OGs; using multipliers (farm extension services or cooperatives) or by setting up regional nodes as local hubs to meet TN partners and facilitate the sharing of needs, information and potential solutions.
- C. The third strategy is to **organize face-to-face (F2F) interviews or perform large-scale consultations or surveys** through existing regional or local networks or channels, e.g. existing farmer consulting systems.
E.g. Agrispin ([Deliverable 1.5](#)) used an innovative storytelling strategy. They started by asking all partners of the consortium to write a story about a farm innovation that they were working on, their role, the journey they had taken so far and the lessons they had learned in their own words. Next, they also collected the dreams of participants during F2F workshops.

2. TN State of The Art:

The TN should also have or gather an **extensive overview of what content already exists (relevant state of the art) in relation to the subject it will deal with and the TN should know how it will utilise the existing** coordination and support measures to apply, add value and go beyond the existing body of knowledge. This phase enables the TN to decide whether they have enough knowledge and expertise within the TN, or whether they need to do more preparatory work or engage other experts (see 3) ([TN content](#)).

3. TN Roadmap:

The TN should have a **flexible roadmap towards the outputs** (e.g. solutions to certain problems) the TN wants to develop, trial and apply. It should **co-create** these outputs **with the best experts** that are required to solve the problems the TN has identified. Once the TN has gathered an overview of knowledge (as described in 2) a TN may identify that external expert knowledge is required.

Here **‘end users’ and enablers (facilitators) should** work together with experts to develop potential outputs and ensure the user friendliness and feasibility of the outputs that are being developed. For example, a TN may identify that they need **different actors** to create an enabling environment **for the actual implementation or upscaling of an output**, such as proper regulation or value chain cooperation. If needed, the **TN should allow actors to flexibly adapt their role in the TN** as the project matures. The TN provides a **2-way knowledge exchange** between all of the involved actors (TN MAA).

4. TN Culture:

It is very important to establish and maintain a good alignment of all actors towards the shared goal(s) of the TN. This is the responsibility of the coordinator, but a facilitator can help to make sure that all involved actors have a **clear view on the process, the intermediate steps and their role within the process**. In the beginning of the project, this should be translated in some sort of TN ‘Code of Conduct’ or rules of engagement to clearly spell out expectations, roles and governance during the trust building phase. Moreover, additional resources should be available to create a culture of trust within a TN through team building exercises to enforce the ‘Code of Conduct’ (TN MAA).

5. TN Facilitation:

The co-creation process should be **facilitated by facilitators with sufficient expertise only**. The facilitator does not need to be an expert in the field of enquiry but must have or build a trusting, respectful relationship with the TN. The role of the facilitator is to guide the TN through the co-creation process, keeping all actors motivated and working together towards their common goal(s). The facilitators’ role is also to help the TN recognise when and what external support or different actors are required. The facilitator should have strong soft & process skills and be able to adapt to the needs of the TN. For example, a newly formed TN may require more directive facilitation to begin with, compared to an established TN which is more self-driven. A facilitator therefore needs to demonstrate competence in facilitating multi-actor knowledge exchange and the ability to reflect and adjust their approach as the TN evolves. The facilitator should map the needs, drivers and competencies of each actor and identify roles which play to their strengths and facilitate the sharing of knowledge and skills between actors (TN MAA).

6. TN Structure:

In addition, the TN should have a **multi-layered structure** in the network considering the **local, national, cross-regional and EU level from start to finish** in order to create **impact at all levels**. There should be dynamic links at the national/EU-level with regular meetings to facilitate communication between each level and overall coordination. Each participating member state should be represented by a consortium partner (TN MAA).

7. TN Content:

The **outputs** that the TN produces should be **based on practical expertise** that can motivate farmers to apply or further innovate to tackle technological, economic and ecological problems. The solutions should have clear targets and user profiles (+ expertise level) for the problems they are trying to solve and they should be **embedded in everyday farming practice**. The role of a TN is (I) to create and share timely practice solutions by leveraging existing knowledge to technological, economic and ecological problems; and (II) to inspire other ‘end users’ and actors to mobilise new TNs or other multi-actor projects (MAPs) to trial, innovate and apply their own practical solutions to context specific problems (TN content).

8. TN Digital Platform:

The **digital platform** that houses the TNs knowledge outputs should function so that the content shown to each user is **profile user led i.e. tailored to their profile, level of expertise and in their preferred language and format** (automatic profiling and translation). This should be organised using common easy language with well-defined

concepts and focus (instead of using overgeneralised buzz-words). Having a digital platform which responds to each user creates trust and validity in the platform, which can amplify the number of users it reaches and the impact it gains (TN content storage + TN content + TN MAA + TN C&D).

9. TN User Interaction:

In addition, the digital platform should **use user analytics** to further optimize its usability, including **evaluation and feedback forms** on the solutions and outputs it generates. For example, via user reviews of content, content suggestions (e.g. Amazon function: ‘user that were interested in this were also interested in these alternatives’) or a ‘bot’ that flags up other information that is relevant for you in an interactive virtual conversation (Q&A). This would facilitate a live, interactive experience for the user and enable the TN **to improve the outputs and adapt them**, so they stay relevant (see the iterative spiral from the ‘Community of Practice’) (TN content storage + TN content + TN MAA + TN C&D).

E.g. 4D4E, measured outreach with user analytics in a learning community E.g. Farm Demo hub that was set up by AgriDemo-F2F, PLAID and Nefertiti uses questions, instead of keywords or categories to guide the users to the results that are most relevant for them.

10. Access to TN Output:

The **digital platform** that houses the TN outputs should provide **easy access** to content through an **optimised search engine** with highly configurable, state-of-the-art search engine technology. In addition, a cross-platform with cross-device applications, such as a user-friendly mobile application for daily use, should be explored. All **content needs to be relevant, to the point and instantly provide value to the user**. Therefore, the content should be easily searchable and findable (TN content storage).

As such, digital platforms of TNs should at least adopt the following **features to filter information** (high signal to noise ratio within a max of 5 clicks):

- A. A good categorization with keywords or “Search Zones” i.e. the existence of specific “areas” on a webpage allowing for guided content search through use of predefined options (geography, sectors, themes, needs, expertise, solutions, content type, origin, date, etc.) when you want to browse and be inspired.
- B. Intuitive and efficient search tools (similar to those that most people use every day provided by major tech firms) when you want to find specifically what you are looking for.

11. TN Output Standardisation:

The outputs of a TN have a **degree of standardisation**, including descriptors and metadata provided by well-established and acknowledged vocabulary, going from tailor-made solutions to highly standardised content depending on who the output is for (TN content storage).

12. TN Community of Practice:

The TN should build and grow an **interactive ‘Community of Practice’** that can refine the solutions and enhance the uptake **in an iterative learning spiral by creating regional pilots and by A/B testing in different regions** to consider regional differences. The TN can build this community from scratch or it can try to involve and leverage existing communities (e.g. farmer networks, cooperatives, NGOs,). It is the facilitators’ role to recognise that an existing community may have very different needs compared to a newly established community and to adjust the approach accordingly. The TN will assign equal weight to the ideas and input from all members of the network, asking questions of end users and valuing everyone’s input, regardless of perceived status. Again, the facilitators’ role is to make sure that everyone is able to contribute to the direction of travel of the TN (TN MA + TN C&D). *E.g. SKIN has developed an online platform for the implementation of a Virtual Community of Practice “Keep it short”, in order to support the existing network and expand it with new end users, but also to exchange news, experiences and ensure the sustainability of the SKIN outputs.*

13. TN Assets Leveraging:

Local and well-established existing networks (e.g. National Rural Networks (NRNs) or OGs), **channels** (e.g. media contacts, news outlets or farmer organisations), **meetings and activities should be used** as much as possible for getting relevant input and organising end user communication and dissemination activities. Farmers & foresters

only interact and take up information from materials, channels and people they trust. This also includes other farmers they respect in their community. Therefore, a **mapping exercise to identify the resources which farmers are using and their existing connections and support mechanisms for TNs is vital to ensure uptake of new information within the TN and wider dissemination throughout the farming community (TN C&D).**

14. TN Digital Support:

The TN should provide **digital support structures** that allow to **share problems, expertise, solutions and that can bring actors together**. This should be done **in an engaging and interactive fashion**, e.g. via a chat forum, WebTV with videos or podcasts to engage young potential farmers and allow farmers to ask each other for help and facilitate questions and sharing of knowledge between users. Potentially, this could be built or interact with existing social media platforms, like Facebook, Instagram or Reddit (e.g. Olivipedia) (**TN content storage + TN MAA + TN C&D**).

15. TN Training:

Nonetheless, the TN should also target ‘analogue users’ and increase the digital literacy of their ‘end users’ via **training/support**. The use of **professional teachers or links to a known and trusted education or training platform** can be an added value. It may also be effective to introduce ‘analogue users’ to digital platforms via traditional forms of knowledge exchange, such as discussion groups or F2F dissemination meetings. Here, the value and benefits of digital platforms can be established as a means of bringing this community back together online (**TN C&D**).

16. TN Peer-To-Peer Exchange:

The TN should consider the **innovation adaptation curve** (innovator > early adopter > majority > laggards) and spend the majority of their focus on those ‘end users’ they can reach that act as **influencers** for the others (80/20-rule). As such, it should have a clear strategy with support tools to leverage this knowledge transfer effect and allow farmers to communicate more with other farmers and exchange ideas via **F2F meetings and cross-visits**. Elements of gamification or organizing an award can also be useful (**TN C&D**).
E.g. Newbie award for new entrant business models as inspiration for other farmers.

17. TN Output Format:

In terms of the format, materials, and tools used for dissemination purposes, **the less text and more visual and interactive the better**. So, there should be a focus on creating **engaging videos of best practices or case examples** with co-created content and international showcases of new information (**TN C&D**).

18. TN Separate Communication & Dissemination:

In order to maximise their impact TNs should have a **clear understanding of the difference between communication & dissemination** (the latter only being focused on promoting the uptake of results). In addition, they should have **separate plans**, tailored and targeted to specific audiences, **with separate monitoring systems** during and after the project execution in place to evaluate their outreach, the usefulness of their outputs, the actual uptake of results and to **estimate their direct and indirect impact** whenever possible (**TN content + TN C&D**).
E.g. Agridemo-F2F did try to analyse impact by doing telephone interviews 6 months after the demos.

19. TN Resources Dissemination:

A major part of the budget and resource allocation should be spent on actual **dissemination**. Potentially even adding a separate project on this **after the project has ended**. This is to maximise the impact of outputs created during the original TN project timeline to benefit the wider farming community. Resources and (financial) incentives to engage ‘end users’ are needed and to connect local OGs across members states in a peer-to-peer fashion (**TN C&D**).

20. TN Sustainability:

The TN should be sustainable and ensure that the **project results stay available** for the intended target audiences and beyond, even after the project has ended. In addition, it should allow actors within the network to stay

connected. This could be facilitated by an online digital platform, or the continuation of meetings organised by the network themselves where they rotate the role of the facilitator. Therefore, TNs need to address this point (the sustainability of the network) including matters related to governance and financing already during the lifetime of the TN (TN content storage).

5. Next steps

Based on the results, recommendations above and the conclusions from Task 2.1, 2.2, 2.3 and 2.4 an impact assessment framework, consisting of quantitative and qualitative criteria) will be made pertaining to the four different aspects of TNs, content, content storage, C&D, and the MAA (D2.6). This will serve as input for WP3 that has to determine harmonised TN approaches and come up with the best design and format for a HIKR.

The recommendations will also be used as a basis for the first discussions with the SCAR SWG AKIS Group (Kaunas; 19-20 November 2019) in preparation of the policy brief that has to be delivered by the end of the project (D5.9). Likewise, the recommendations will also serve as a first step and a basis for the meeting of the Strategic Innovation Board (SIB) (Bruges, 31 January 2020) on the Vision Paper on HIKRs.

ANNEX I: Budapest Workshop Program

WORKSHOP IN BUDAPEST

11th-12th -13th September 2019

EURAKNOS

*Connecting Thematic Networks as Knowledge Reservoirs towards a European Agricultural Knowledge Innovation
Open Source System*

*This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817863.*

Day 1 – What is a Thematic Network?

12:00 Welcome lunch

13:00 - 13:30 Introduction of EURAKNOS to the participants

Presenter: Pieter Spanoghe

13:30 - 15:00 Welcome exercise: getting to know each other

Facilitators: Laurens Van der Cruyssen, Davino Van Hal and Nathan De Geyter Transcribers: Elena Feo, Els Berckmoes and Merete Studnitz

15:00 - 15:15 Coffee break

15:15 - 15:45 What is a TN?

Presenter: Pieter Spanoghe

15:45 - 17:15 The ideal TN Exercise

Facilitators: Laurens Van der Cruyssen, Davino Van Hal and Nathan De Geyter

17:30 Closing day1

18:30 Dinner and networking

Day 2 – As is situation for Thematic Networks

9:00 Introduction day 2: Wrap up Day 1 and presentation of agenda Day 2

Presenter Sylvia Burssens

9:15- 10:45 The communication and dissemination of the Thematic Network Presentation

Presenter Pauline Bodin

9:45 - 10:45 Discussion about Communication & Dissemination in 3 different groups

Facilitators: Laurens Van der Cruyssen, Davino Van Hal and Nathan De Geyter

10:45 - 11:00 Coffee break

11:00 - 11:30 Presentation on TN Data & Content

Presenter: Rosa Mosquera Losada

11:30 -12:30 Workshop on TN Data & Content

Facilitators: Laurens Van der Cruyssen, Davino Van Hal and Nathan De Geyter

12:30 - 13:30 Lunch and networking

13:30 - 14:00 Evaluation of the design of Knowledge Reservoirs within Thematic Networks

Presenter: Maxime Marois

14:00 - 15:00 Discussion on the design of Knowledge Reservoirs within Thematic Network in 3 different groups

Facilitators: Laurens Van der Cruyssen, Davino Van Hal and Nathan De Geyter

15:00- 15:15 Coffee break

15:30 - 16:00 Presentation on Multi Actor Approach Presenter: Elodie Pascal

16:00 - 17:00 Discussion in Multi Actor Approach in 3 different groups

Facilitators: Laurens Van der Cruyssen, Davino Van Hal and Nathan De Geyter

17:00- 17:15 Main conclusions and main questions of the day

18:30 Dinner and networking

Day 3 - The future Thematic Network

9:00 - 9:15 Introduction day 3

9:15 The future TN workshop

Facilitator: Laurens Van der Cruyssen

12:15 Closing remarks

Pieter Spanoghe

12:30 Lunch

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817863.

ANNEX II: Presentations

Introduction of EURAKNOS to the participants

EURAKNOS

Thematic network
coordinated by Pieter Spanoghe (Ugent)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817863.

WHY, WHAT, HOW

- ❖ You belong to a certain group of actors (colours)
- ❖ GDPR
 - Recording, filming, transcription
- ❖ Not anonymous
- ❖ WIFI NOVOTEL
- ❖ Sign your presence

TWITTER/LINKEDIN/INSTAGRAM/FACEBOOK

Follow @euraknos

Use the hasthags:

#TNcommunity

#AgriKnowledge

#EURAKNOS

POLL EVERYWHERE Poll Everywhere

Poll Everywhere: <https://PollEv.com/pieterspanog939/register>

Chose the option: [Create an account](#)

Fill in your E-mail, password, first name and last name.

For people who want to work on their smartphone, you can find the application in the app store.

How are you feeling today?

WHAT'S A THEMATIC NETWORK ?

Thematic networks are a new approach under Horizon 2020

which bring people from both science and practice together

to create useful and practical outputs for farmers

on a specific theme within agricultural research and innovation

EURAKNOS GOAL

WHY ?

- To strengthen the EU agricultural knowledge base

HOW ?

- By co-creating « the network to connect all thematic networks »

WHAT ?

- To explore the feasibility of creating a modular database of useful findings from various thematic networks

THE ADDED-VALUE FOR THEMATIC NETWORKS

- Enhance their own impacts
- Uptake of their results by the end-users, farmers, foresters, advisors
- Multiply the channels of communication and dissemination
- Increase the visibility

EURAKNOS

OUR ORGANISATION

17 PARTNERS 200 ORGANISATIONS

EURAKNOS

EURAKNOS TODAY... EUREKA TOMORROW

Call: H2020-RUR-2019-1
Type of action: CSA
Proposal number: 862790
Proposal acronym: Eureka
Duration (months): 24
Proposal title: European
Knowledge repository for best
agricultural practices
Activity: RUR-17-2019

 EURAKNOS
EUROPEAN KNOWLEDGE REPOSITORY FOR BEST AGRICULTURAL PRACTICES

SUBSCRIBE TO OUR NEWSLETTER
AVAILABLE IN 10 LANGUAGES

Subscribe to receive newsletters and relevant news.

Email Address:

Country:

Preferred language:

Profession:

**THANK YOU
FOR YOUR
ATTENTION!**

What is a TN?

EURAKNOS

Thematic network
coordinated by Pieter Spanoghe (Ugent)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817863.

WHAT'S A THEMATIC NETWORK ?

Thematic networks are a new approach under *Horizon 2020*

which bring people from both science and practice together

 to create useful and practical outputs for farmers

on a specific theme within **agricultural research** and **innovation**

COLLECT EXISTING SCIENTIFIC KNOWLEDGE AND BEST PRACTICES

WHICH ARE CLOSE TO BEING PUT INTO PRACTICE, BUT NOT YET SUFFICIENTLY READY FOR FARMERS AND FORESTERS TO IMPLEMENT;

Translate this knowledge into easily understandable end-user material

such as short, informative recommendations and solutions, leaflets, guidelines and audio-visual.

Thematic Networks lead to a better uptake of existing solutions across Europe

CONNECTION

EXCHANGE

KNOWLEDGE

PRACTICE

IMPACT

COLLABORATION

- 1) **Choose the right theme**
 - ✓ Partners choose a specific theme on need identified by farmers, foresters or agribusiness
- 2) **Find complementary partners**
 - ✓ Multi actor approach, complementary types of knowledge (scientific, practical and other)
- 3) **The benefits**
 - ✓ Deliver practical information easy to understand and to apply
- 4) **Disseminate results**
 - ✓ Practice abstracts

BUILD UP A THEMATIC NETWORK

THEMATIC NETWORKS COMMUNITY IS HERE

**THANK YOU
FOR YOUR
ATTENTION!**

The communication and dissemination of the Thematic Network

EURAKNOS

Dissemination & communication analysis

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817863.

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS REMINDER

- 26 TN analyzed under 29
- Keep in mind we're dealing with **different topics, objective, target groups & degree of completion**
- **Limit of the analyse:** based on C&D responsible partners, and not end-user point of view

The communication activities should be focused on the outputs and the results, rather than on the project itself (activities of partners, progress, composition of consortium..).

Absolutely not
Rather not
Somewhat
Absolutely

The dissemination activities should be focused on the outputs and the results, rather than on the project itself (activities of partners, progress, composition of consortium..).

Absolutely not
Rather not
Somewhat
Absolutely

COMMUNICATION & DISSEMINATION PLAN

- 84% have developed a strategy
- 56% are making a difference between communication & dissemination

REMINDER OF THE FORMAL DEFINITION

Communication

- Promote action and results
- Multiple audience
- Make the research activities understood
- Address public policy

Dissemination

- Make the results public
- Make real results used
- Any appropriate means

A SUCCESSFUL COMMUNICATION & DISSEMINATION STRATEGY

- > How to define the success ?
- > How to measure it?

"The end goal is that best practice is implemented, that end-users receive the information in a positive spirit and promote the project results/platform to their peers."

OTHER PROMISING SUCCESSFUL CHANNELS

- EVENTS, CONFERENCES
- WEBINARS PROGRAMS
- RADIO
- DEMONSTRATION
- WHATS APP (EMERGING TOOL)

THIS LOGO MAKES YOU THINK ABOUT...

This logo makes you think about...

Don't forget to use the correct logo for your content. Get the logo content from the app or get help at [Pedia.com/faq](#)

2) USE DIFFERENT CHANNELS TO REACH END USERS

3) DESIGN SPECIFIC MATERIALS FOR END USERS

Researchers	Students	Local policy makers	National policy makers	International policy makers	Advisors
<input type="checkbox"/> Newsletters	<input type="checkbox"/> Newsletters	<input type="checkbox"/> Press release	<input type="checkbox"/> Press release	<input type="checkbox"/> Video	<input type="checkbox"/> Practice abstracts
<input type="checkbox"/> Practice abstracts	<input type="checkbox"/> Courses	<input type="checkbox"/> Video	<input type="checkbox"/> Newsletters	<input type="checkbox"/> Newsletter	<input type="checkbox"/> Newsletters
<input type="checkbox"/> Fact sheets	<input type="checkbox"/> Articles/ Scientific papers	<input type="checkbox"/> Newsletters	<input type="checkbox"/> Fact sheets	<input type="checkbox"/> Press release	<input type="checkbox"/> Fact sheets
<input type="checkbox"/> Press release	<input type="checkbox"/> Practice abstracts	<input type="checkbox"/> Video	<input type="checkbox"/> Video	<input type="checkbox"/> Practice Abstract	<input type="checkbox"/> Press release
<input type="checkbox"/> Video	<input type="checkbox"/> Fact sheets			<input type="checkbox"/> Fact sheets	<input type="checkbox"/> Video

Consumers	Farmers	Farmers association	Industries
<input type="checkbox"/> Video	<input type="checkbox"/> Practice abstracts	<input type="checkbox"/> Practice abstracts	<input type="checkbox"/> Newsletter
<input type="checkbox"/> Newsletter	<input type="checkbox"/> Newsletters	<input type="checkbox"/> Articles	<input type="checkbox"/> Practice Abstract
<input type="checkbox"/> Article	<input type="checkbox"/> Video	<input type="checkbox"/> Video	<input type="checkbox"/> Fact sheets
<input type="checkbox"/> Press release	<input type="checkbox"/> Fact sheets		<input type="checkbox"/> Video

EDUCATION PROGRAMS

BEST VISUALS

Under 19 answers

BEST PRACTICES ON VIDEOS

4) END-USERS ENGAGEMENT

Did you make an explicit effort to optimize internal communication (between partners)?

Absolutely not

Rather not

Somewhat

Absolutely

Which efforts do you use to optimize internal communication (word cloud will be presented).

Do you think efforts on internal communication impacts the way end users receive information?

Absolutely not

Rather not

Somewhat

Absolutely

An organization with excellent internal communication will run smoothly, allowing its members to progress toward a mutual goal, which will ultimately affect the quality of external communication.

THANK YOU FOR YOUR ATTENTION!

- ### WORKSHOPS
- 1) How to reach end-users, and especially farmers? How to keep them engaged?
 - 2) How to adapt the content according to different end users?

- ### 2) HOW TO ADAPT THE CONTENT ACCORDING TO DIFFERENT END USERS?
- Target the communication to the profile
 - Identify the needs

Practice-led innovation supported by science and market-driven actors in the laying hen and other livestock sectors
 HORIZON 2020-2024 project, Grant no. 810232

EXAMPLES

Project overview

The HENNOVATION project was the first thematic network funded under the topic ISB 2 'Closing the research and innovation divide: the critical role of innovation support systems and knowledge exchange of the Horizon 2020 EU Research and Innovation programme, implemented from January 2015 to August 2017. Facing the laying hen sector as a case study, the HENNOVATION project demonstrated the potential of innovation led by farmers and industry practices in two areas of concern: Intra- and Inter- and End-of-line, during transport and at the abattoir. This was realised through the establishment of in-line for innovation networked different levels of the production chain, local, national and European level in five countries (United Kingdom, Sweden, The Netherlands, Spain and The Czech Republic). These networks are actively supported by and shared the aims to make the industry more efficient and sustainable. These networks were supported by science driven actors, such as veterinary surgeons, farm advisors and scientists, researchers, and market-driven actors, such as those that sell eggs (e.g. retailers, packers, food processors), and those selling egg production (farm assurance, certification schemes). The overarching aim of these networks was to generate and disseminate innovations based on practice, and supported with scientific and scientific information to increase sustainability of the laying hen sector.

Technical Resources

The research work carried out as part of the project revealed that the practice-led approach promoted by the project can be a great stimulus for innovation. Intra- and inter- or in-g. new type of litter material to reduce stress and encourage natural behaviour in the use of digital systems to reduce antibiotic use, a variety of other tech resources and different approaches, all innovative and emergent through these networks. These were related to product or process to, e.g. a new way of monitoring Poultry Feed Use Reduction and new relationships between value chain actors, to increase the public trust.

Partners

A variety of materials were developed for the support actors engaged with the networks. These included working scientific literature, peer-reviewed knowledge such as expert reviews on Intra- and Inter- and End-of-line, an online training course, 3D Practice Abstracts and the Technical notes. Guidelines for network facilitation and a HENNOVATION video, explained the practice-led approach, were also developed to support networks for farmers. All these materials can be found on this website.

Advisory Board

The work done by the project suggests that successful multi-scale practice-led innovation networks depend on **active participation** from all involved, **professional facilitation**, **moderate resource support** and **access to relevant expertise**. From the research work, there is a clear need for opportunities and challenges exist for the development of a more sustainable and practice-led model of innovation in sustainable agricultural systems. And that recognising the value of the type of innovation as 'science' and its product as 'innovation' is a significant step in resolving the longstanding and enduring 'science/innovation gap'.

News & Events

Links

Contact Us

Innoseta - Thematic Network
 90 abonnés
 7 mois

...

#Innoseta website is now available in all 7 Hub languages! Visit www.innoseta.eu and subscribe to our Newsletter to keep in touch!

#spraying #equipment #training #advising #thematicnetwork #H2020

Voir la traduction

5

J'aime Commenter Partager

Soyez le premier à commenter ceci

A different idea of bread

MARC DEVALQUE, baker

Sélections | A different idea of bread

8 vues

1 0 0 PARTAGER 0 S'ABONNER

Genève Project
Publié le 17 mai 2019

ABONNÉ 31

EURAKNOS

TN Outputs

Maria Rosa Mosquera-Losada, Dario Arias Martinez,
Nuria Ferreiro-Dominguez, Maria Jesús Taboada Iglesias,
Maria Elena Mosquera-Losada, José Javier Santiago Freijanes

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817863.

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS: EXISTING KNOWLEDGE

- Context: Land use, Farming systems, Farm Management
- Type of Output Production
- Geographic distribution
- Synergies

TOPICS

Topic	Percentage
Arable	45.5%
Not associated land	13.6%
Forestry	13.0%
Permanent Grassland	31.8%
Permanent crops	40.9%
Agroforestry	18.2%

Large content on Croplands Livestock large degree of completion range

LOCATION

RURAL AND LOWLANDS

FARM ORGANIZATION

COOPERATIVES mixed with FAMILY FARMING COLLECTIVE FARMING

FARM ORGANIZATION

Mixed large/Small mainly traditional

FARM EMPLOYMENT

Full time and Women farmers

FARMING SYSTEM

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS: EXISTING KNOWLEDGE

- Context: Land use, Farming systems, Farm Management
- Type of Output Production
- Geographic distribution
- Synergies Synergies and Sustainability of TN

LAYOUT: DATA OUTPUT CATEGORY

Not related with the degree of completion

LAYOUT: DATA ORIGIN

CONTENT: DATA ORIGIN. ACTIVITIES

LAYOUT:

- Identify the best tools to communicate
- Identify the best tools to disseminate
- Defining the type of documents produced
- Associate them to the Dissemination and Communication

DEFINITIONS. DISSEMINATION MATERIAL

Main type of outputs. Dissemination	
Practice abstracts	A short document that highlights a practice and useful innovation. Target: Farmers and researchers
Factsheets	One single printed sheet with a concise presentation of information in a format which emphasizes key points concisely, usually using tables, bullet points and/or headings and printed on a single printed page. They are sometimes a summary of a longer document. Target: Farmers and researchers
Research papers,, Reviews	Papers published in scientific journals indexed in the WoS or any other scientific database as a direct result (Research papers) or as a compilation of results from other papers. Target: Researchers
Report	A document coming from the project that highlights the most important results from a specific project Target: Researchers
Technical articles	A document that describes the nature, state of the art, progress, or results of a technical process. Therefore usually associated to best practices. Target: Farmers
Guides	A document that describes a process or the know-how of an innovation. Target: Farmers
Videos	A film detailing an innovation in images. Target: Farmers
Handbook	A book giving information such as facts on a particular subject or instructions for operating a machine. Target: All type of stakeholders

DEFINITIONS

Main type of Outputs. Communication	
Press release	Official statement delivered to members of the news media for the purpose of providing information, an official statement or making an announcement. To maximize the impact it could be linked to the provision of a solution of a huge society problem. Target: General Public
Brochure, booklets	A type of small magazine that contains pictures and information on the project. Target: General Public
Podcast	Audio that is stored in a digital form that you can download from the internet and play on a computer. Target: General Public
Infographics	A representation of information in a graphic format designed to make the data easily understandable at a glance. Target: General Public
Newsletter	a bulletin issued periodically to the members of the project. Target: General Public

CAN WE VALIDATE?

COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION INFOGRAPHICS BASED ON DOCUMENTS

DOCUMENT DEFINITIONS AND USEFULNESS

ALL PRODUCED ALL TRANSLATED

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS: EXISTING KNOWLEDGE

- Content: Land use, Farming systems, Farm Management
- Type of Output Production
- Geographic distribution
- Synergies Synergies and Sustainability of TN

HOW CAN WE EXPAND SPECIFIC SECTOR KNOWLEDGE TOWARDS THOSE LESS REPRESENTED COUNTRIES BASED ON THEIR OWN NEEDS

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS: EXISTING KNOWLEDGE

- Content: Land use, Farming systems, Farm Management
- Type of Output Production
- Geographic distribution
- Synergies and Sustainability of TN

METHODOLOGY

Counting of words related to each sector:

- a) arable crop,
- b) permanent crop,
- c) permanent grassland (livestock) and
- d) forestry

but.... some of them not allocated....

WHAT ARE THE KNOWLEDGE GAPS?
HOW CAN WE IMPROVE THE CONNECTION BETWEEN TN,
AND OG?

SUSTAINABILITY

SUSTAINABILITY

WHAT ARE THE BEST FORM TO INCREASE SUSTAINABILITY?

- * INNOVATION DOCUMENT MAINTENANCE AND INCREASE
- * INNOVATION NETWORKING MAINTENANCE AND ENLARGEMENT

**THANK YOU
FOR YOUR
ATTENTION!**

Evaluation of the design of Knowledge Reservoirs within Thematic Networks

EURAKNOS

Evaluation of the design of Knowledge Reservoirs within Thematic Network

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 617563.

THE MAIN OBJECTIVES

Draw up an inventory of what the Thematic Networks (TNs) have produced in terms of knowledge:
How each of them has developed its Knowledge Reservoir (KR) in order to make this knowledge available?

Keep in mind: with Euraknos' project, we are dealing in a **very short time** with **different TNs on various topics and degree of completion.**

EURAKNOS' APPROACH

Carrying out comparative surveys on evaluation of the format and the design of the **21 TNs** analyzed out of **28** existing TNs
Based on **KR responsible partners' interviews**

The purpose of this presentation is to make sure that we share the vision and to highlight the diversity of KR

INTRODUCTION

DEFINITION OF BASIC CONCEPTS

What is a Knowledge Reservoir?

A **knowledge reservoir (KR)** is a collection of best materials, practices, instruments, methodologies and tools, that contribute to the use of innovative solutions for sustainable agriculture and forestry.

(reference: the EURAKNOS' project)

A KR is like a virtual library

INTRODUCTION

DEFINITION OF BASIC CONCEPTS

What is the basic format of a TN website?

- General information about the project
- In-house productions and information (deliverables, fact sheet,...)
- List of partners involved in the project
- List of contacts
- Agenda (news and events related to the project)

FREQUENCY OF WEBSITE UPDATES

One general observation, the update strategy is totally dependent on the phases of the project

WEEKLY: new content is added at the start of the project

MONTHLY: when the project is half way through

ANNUALLY: the project has ended; updates are less significant

CRITERIA SELECTED FOR SEARCH OPTIONS

KR'S BUILDERS (CONSTRUCTION AND DEVELOPMENT)

The "contributors" of knowledge versus the IT developers

The "contributors" of knowledge are involved in both of the construction and development of the KR. Contributors include all the partners involved in the project.

They are the main actors of the project and the only ones who can define their needs in terms of IT development.

*: project coordinator + WP leader + partner

WHAT ARE THE NECESSARY TECHNOLOGICAL CHOICES?

The choice of the Content Management System is a very technical question (few answers: 12 on 21 TNs).

Note: this is an important choice as it greatly conditions the possibilities of features offered.

However 75% of respondents are satisfied with their choice.

KR'S ACCESS

Limited or not limited?

To the question: « Is an accreditation required to access the data on your TN's KR? »

→ 41% of the answers are positive

Is accreditation really necessary? What for?

RATING SYSTEM

58% use website traffic analytics

It is the most used tool because it works on any website

success criteria: number of downloads / number of individual visitors per month.

17% use end-users survey

The goal: understand what users are looking for in terms of content

17% use social media tools

A way to promote some contents

8% use other means

Specific rating system
End-user scoring system
possibility to leave a comment

Learn a little
Your email address will not be published. Required fields are marked *

Comment

Name *

Email *

Website

By using this form you agree with the storage and handling of your data by this website.

KR LANGUAGES

Barriers	Level access	Observed practices
1 st	Access to the website	English always comes up first
2 nd	Access to the KR	50% in English only 41% in the languages of the project partners 9% in other languages (using Google translation tools)
3 rd	Access to the contents	38% in English only 42% in the languages of the project partners

KNOWLEDGE RESERVOIR MAPPING

DIFFERENT DESIGNS FOR DIFFERENT KR

Some KR's are based on:

- End-users requests and needs
- Type of contents which can be scientific or not so scientific, very « hands-on » with lots of tips and forums
- Input from partners and users (videos, etc...)

The e-KRP should be more than a library, it should be an online workspace to create content

yes

no

Search the presentation to see the content. Get the full content? Install the app or get help at PHILIA.com/help

e-KRP users should have a viewable profile page (by other e-KRP users) on the e-KRP

yes

no

Search the presentation to see the content. Get the full content? Install the app or get help at PHILIA.com/help

e-KRP users should be able to communicate with each other on the e-KRP?

yes

no

Search the presentation to see the content. Get the full content? Install the app or get help at PHILIA.com/help

KR AS A CATALOGUE : CHOOSE YOUR INNOVATION

Search engine

Argument

Contents: HTML and PDF stored on the KR...

KR AS A LIBRARY : FIND THE KNOWLEDGE ON THE RIGHT SHELVES

Entry

Dartmoor, The UK

Contents: Documents mainly in PDF...

KR AS A PRACTICAL DIGITAL GUIDE BOOK

Search engine

Contents: Diversity of contents: PDF, HTML, videos...

KR AS A MARKET PLACE TO EXCHANGE GOOD PRACTICES

Links to suppliers

Contents: URL Links directed to private web sites, social networks...

THE FUTURE KNOWLEDGE RESERVOIR

EURAKNOS' CONTRIBUTION

EURAKNOS has an important role to play in proposing and providing solutions in:

- updating the KR
- choosing a content management system (CMS)
- the KR's sustainability
- thinking about a storage logic that takes into account the needs of the potential users

OTHER E-KRP INITIATIVES (NO TNS)

- investigate existing similar initiatives at national and international level
- explore the feasibility and added value of developing an own e-KRP
- explore the feasibility of connect and communicate with existing e-KRP

OTHER E-KRP INITIATIVES (NO TNS)

- Ask-Valerie
- FarmDemo platform
- EIP-AGRI website
- Organic Farm Knowledge
- FAO Agroecology Knowledge Hub
- FAO Family Farming Knowledge Platform
- Panorama Solutions
- Sustainable Intensification Platform
- AccessAgriculture
- Smartchain

Start the presentation to activate live content
If you see this message in presentation mode, install the add-in or get help at [Ppts.com/app](https://ppts.com/app)

**THANK YOU
FOR YOUR
ATTENTION**

AND

**FOR YOUR
INVOLVEMENT
IN THIS WORKSHOP**

Multi Actor Approach

EURAKNOS

TASK 2.4 Multi-actor strategy results analysis

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817863.

ORAL SURVEY/ GENERAL FRAMEWORK

- Size of the sample: 18 TNs on 28 (if no answers) are excluded from the analytics
- Huge diversity of topics
- Huge diversity of target groups/end-users/
- Various projects' degrees of completion
- Many qualitative data (open questions)

INTRODUCTION

- What is the definition of MA in the literature vs how is the MAA determined in TNs' reality?
- What is the interpretation of MA by the participants of TNs?
- Focus on farmers as end-users: are they well represented in the MAA of the TNs?
- How to better ensure the sustainability of the TNs? What role does / shall a MA approach play in the sustainability of a TN's work?

DEFINITION MAA (SOURCE: EIP-AGRI 2019)

Many Horizon 2020 calls require projects to apply the "multi-actor approach". This means that projects must focus on real problems or opportunities that farmers and foresters are facing.

It also means that partners with complementary types of knowledge – scientific, practical and other – must join forces in the project activities from beginning to end.

[HTTPS://EC.EUROPA.EU/EIP/AGRICULTURE/EN/NEWS/BROCHURES-MULTI-ACTOR-APPROACH](https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/news/brochures-multi-actor-approach)

Does the MAA increase impact?

Absolutely not

Rather not

Somewhat

Absolutely

Start the presentation to see the content, click on the content to read the app or go help at Public.com/app

Is working together with multiple actors on a common task the real bottleneck of success of a TN?

Absolutely not

Rather not

Somewhat

Absolutely

Start the presentation to see the content, click on the content to read the app or go help at Public.com/app

CONSTRAINT OR OPPORTUNITY?

WELL BALANCED OR SOME ACTORS DO MOST OF THE WORK?

WHAT IS YOUR 'FEELING' ABOUT WORKING IN A MULTI-ACTOR GROUP?

ACCORDING TO YOU, WHAT MAKES IT SUCCESSFUL?

MAA FROM YOUR POINT OF VIEW?

THE MAA IN PRACTICE

- Broad range of answers
- Some TN proposals used directly the definition findable in H2020 projects
- Some other TNs made their 'own definition'
- for all TNs, MAA is understood as a mix of different types of actors with different backgrounds
- The structure of the MA group varies for each project
- It depends of the history, context, aim of the project (previous existing networks, context of the innovation carried out, purpose of the innovation, end-users targeted...)

PRELIMINARY QUESTIONS ABOUT MAA

Question	Percentage of YES
Did you have a clear reference about stakeholders in your TN proposal?	81.5%
Did you have a clear reference about the potential end-users of the innovation in your TN proposal?	81.5%
Did the transition towards actor approach offered in your TN proposal will be carried out personally?	52.2%

Most TNs representatives interviewed consider that they had a clear definition of what stands behind the term of multi actor in their TN proposal

More than a half of the TN representatives evaluate that the MAA approach has differed or evolved during the project lifetime

Most TNs representatives interviewed affirm that the potential end-users were well determined in the proposal

WHO ARE THE POTENTIAL END-USERS?

Group	Percentage
farmers	90%
farmers associations	75%
advisors	80%
extension services	10%
policy makers	25%
researchers	25%
facilitators	10%

Shall future tns consider more often policy makers as end users?

Absolutely not

Rather not

Somewhat

Absolutely

How can future tns consider more often policy makers as end users (word cloud)?

MAJOR DIFFICULTIES ACCORDING TO THE INTERVIEWED TNS CONTACTS

WHAT TYPE OF OTHER DIFFICULTIES DID YOU EXPERIENCE?

...

...

...

Recommendations?

- ...
- ...
- ...

HOW CAN WE OVERCOME THESE HURDLES?

CONTRIBUTION OF THE MAA GROUP

For the question about „did the contribution of the MA group change over the project lifetime?“ statistics include the possible change for some actors while there is no change for others.

THE INVOLVEMENT OF ACTORS CHANGED OVER THE PROJECT FOR

Should different actors have different weights in decision depending on their level of expertise?

Absolutely not

Rather not

Somewhat

Absolutely

ACCORDING TO YOUR OPINION, HOW CAN WE EXPLAIN THE CHANGE OF INVOLVEMENT (+ OR -) FOR FARMERS ?

- ...
- ...
- ...

HOW DID THE THEMATIC NETWORK KEEP FARMERS ENGAGED IN MEETINGS?

- Choose a **comfortable area** to set the meeting for farmers (good atmosphere, coffee, food...) contact (phonically, whatsapp) them several times so they don't forget the meeting
- Throw the **study visits** for farmers
- Focus on **commercial aspects** (not research)
- Through the national steering boards. They decide on the topics to be discussed in the project. These topics should trigger the farmers. Annual contest focusing on farmers.
- Interesting topics and facilitation. Free access
- Try to have an **informal part** in every meetings... with drinks for example, to have a social part.

ACCORDING TO YOU, WHAT ELSE KEEP FARMERS ENGAGED IN MEETINGS?

Does your TN involve actors who act as innovation brokers?

yes

no

Start the presentation to see the content. Select the content, install the app or get help at [Public.com/faq](#)

What is an innovation broker (word cloud)?

Start the presentation to see the content. Select the content, install the app or get help at [Public.com/faq](#)

WHAT IS YOUR BEST ADVICE TO ENGAGE FARMERS IN EVENTS

- Having good **innovation brokers** that are trusted by farmers. Contact them frequently
- Use the **advisory services** in order to select the **right innovative farmers**, look for a win-win situation: what are the farmers' drivers or barriers? Combine "more boring topics" with catchy topics for farmers
- Talk, F2F meetings and interview with the farmers. Public talks with farmers. The best way to engage farmers is talk with them. No presentations, **no official speeches**.
- Project events/meetings can be combined with other events so farmers are triggered to come as they will visit the other event.

ANNEX III: Methodology and Results

Day 1 (12:00 - 17:30)

13:00 - 13:30 Introduction of EURAKNOS to the participants

Presenter: Pieter Spanoghe

Why, what, how of the Euraknos project, the participant's role in the workshops, as well as the colour coding system we applied to have different categories of participants: organisers, TNs, and whether they gave permission to be filmed or not/GDPR, twitter.

13:30 - 15:00 Welcome exercise

Facilitators: Laurens Van der Cruyssen, Davino Van Hal and Nathan De Geyter Transcribers: Elena Feo, Els Berckmoes and Merete Studnitz

The plenary group was divided into 3 groups. Every participant filled out a profile card (10min), which they then presented to the group and subsequently these cards were hung in a dedicated space as a reference the participants could use to network and explore, it worked as a good starting point to start conversations between people. Next to their profile, participants also had to name the 3 biggest challenges in agriculture and also the 3 main challenges for TNs.

NAME: _____		
Country _____	Thinking _____	Doing _____
Job _____	Digi-beginner _____	Digi-expert _____
Hobbies _____	Generalist _____	Specialist _____
_____	Beer _____	Wine _____
_____	Forest _____	Beach _____
ONE INTERESTING STORY ABOUT YOUR JOB	3 BIGGEST CHALLENGES IN AGRICULTURE/FORESTRY	3 BIGGEST CHALLENGES FOR TN'S

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Template: Profile card

Results:

Group 1

What are the 3 biggest challenges in agriculture/forestry?

- Adopting new technologies
- Innovation uptake in practice
- Climate change
- Food production that is sustainable (for farmers and the environment)
- The environment: bio-diversity and circular ecology
- Continuation of the occupation: generational renewal
- More value from products: connecting consumers to the production chain
- Pests: output uncertainty
- Clear rules and policies

What are the 3 biggest challenges for TNs?

- End users: reaching and understanding them
- Measuring impact
- Disseminating knowledge
- Using a common language to transfer practical knowledge
- Sustainability of the TN, its knowledge and the project, keeping the momentum going
- Distance, language and meeting each other
- Recreating knowledge
- Time
- Spreading innovation and new developments
- Engagement of actors
- Co-creating knowledge
- Creating useful information

Group 2

What are the 3 biggest challenges in agriculture/forestry?

- Collecting data
- Climate-friendly production IIII
- Agroforestry III
- Business model of extensive farming I
- Social acceptance
- Make farming sexy for youth - generation shift II
- Antibiotics I
- Brexit (politics)
- Sustainability III
- Share expertise
- Cost of production + cost of innovation III
- Soil care
- Water use
- Implementing innovation II
- digitization and precision farming I

What are the 3 biggest challenges for TNs?

- Unclear focus
- Better management
- Search ability of output
- Relevance and timing of results
- Different country needs I
- MAA and involving farmers IIII
- Longevity after end of the project IIII
- How to best go from theory to practice
- Language and speaking the same jargon III
- Take into account feedback from farmers
- How to measure impact ensure uptake of results I
- User-friendliness of outputs III
- Disseminate knowledge outside of the TN II
- Link with OGs

Group 3

- *What are the 3 biggest challenges for TNs?*

- Sustainability of a TN
- Challenging timeline
- Language
- Common understanding between regions
- End-user focus
- End-user engagement during meetings
- Working together with partners
- Finding partners that are active
- Finding ‘multipliers’ for dissemination on a national level
- Translations between research & real life application
- Co-creating knowledge
- Understanding Knowledge gaps
- Reuse what’s working in a TN (sharing TN best practices)
- Sharing among TNs
- Communication vs. GDPR compliance
- Building trust (social part of a TN)
- Dissemination: what is a TN & its activities
- Including the voices of ‘unusual’ suspects: small farmers / underprivileged farmers
- Building an IT system decentralized
- UX/UI

In the next session, participants (in three groups) were asked about their *expectations on the workshop*.

Results

Group 1

- When it provides requirements for a common platform and recommendations for future TNs
- When able to learn from other TNs
- When I expand my own TN
- Learning new approaches
- When getting lots of input from participants to project partners
- When meeting new contacts and networking
- When getting feedback on the impact of my TN
- When hearing about success stories about sharing discoveries within a TN with others/outside world
- When getting ideas on how to maintain a virtual network for exchange /mutual coaching
- When discovering Hungarian food
- When having interesting network opportunities
- Ideas for partial implementation
- When getting a clear view with regard to who the involved actors are, what types of outputs have been produced, who the targeted end users for TN-outputs are
- When learning more about the view of farmers and advisors
- When knowing how to interesting and useful TNs
- When having clear and shared concepts
- When connecting to people working in the same field
- When knowing how to organise TN activities in the best way
- When the EURAKNOS consortium will understand which are the needs of the present TNs and see if EURAKNOS can help and how

Group 2

Sharing best practices, learning from each other's insights, helping EURAKNOS, to see Budapest.

Group 3

When will this meeting be a success for you?

- Learn from EURAKNOS
- Know more about EURAKNOS achievements
- Support the EURAKNOS implementation
- Learn from each other
- Get new information about TN (objectives, materials)
- Get new ideas for other TNs
- Recognize different aspects & experiences for efficient TN management
- Insights about TN functioning & best practices
- Building on the experience of end-user groups that are present here
- If we can share all our experiences, strengths & weaknesses of TNs and how to improve them
- Meeting other TNs, getting contacts III
- A better cooperation between the TNs
- Better modularity & interoperability between the TNs
- Seeing better interaction among RN & innovation implementation

- If participants feel empowered, believe TNs to be strong & successful tool towards a sustainable Agriculture / Forestry
- Progress in the EURAKNOS project
- Working on the EURAKNOS deliverable for this meeting
- Understand better the MA processes in TNs, in order to start designing a useful HIKR that is used by end users

15:00 - 15:15 Coffee break

15:15 - 15:45 What is a TN?

Presenter: Pieter Spanoghe

15:45 - 17:15 The ideal TN

Facilitators: Laurens Van der Cruyssen, Davino Van Hal and Nathan De Geyter

Transcribers: Elena Feo, Els Berckmoes and Merete Studnitz

During the ideal TN workshop the plenary session was separated into 3 groups. Each participant got the role of an agriculture journalist doing research on the Ideal TN. They got about 10-15 minutes to write an article about the ideal TN, afterwards they got 2-3 minutes each to present their ideal TN. The facilitator wrote down elements mentioned by the participants and created a cover for a magazine in which the ideal TN was published. The 3 posters were discussed by the facilitators on day 3.

Text: "We've just heard what a TN is, several amongst you have some experience being part of a TN, others might not but might have an idea of a TN at this moment. Now it's time to let your imaginations run wild. We're going to create the ideal TN, the ultimate TN of TN's. In order to do this you'll get the role of an investigative agriculture journalist for the EURAKNOS Journal. You've discovered what you think is the ideal TN, and you're going to describe it in your article. Here are some questions that might help you describe the ideal TN you have in your mind. You don't have to answer all of them, but use them as inspiration."

Possible questions the participants could tackle in their article

- *What are the top priorities of this ideal TN?*
- *What are their main activities?*
- *Who is involved in this ideal network? How are they involved?*
- *Who are their end users?*
- *How do they reach their different end users?*
- *How do they keep their end users engaged?*
- *How do they make use of digital technology to better help their end users?*
- *At what level does the ideal TN function? Regional level, national level, European level, mixed.*
- *How do they connect to other TNs? At different levels?*
- *How do they connect to Operational Groups (OGs) and National Rural Networks (NRN)?*

Article: The ideal TN

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Results

Group 1

Digital

- A portal to showcase problems and solutions
- A forum or a chat which allows interaction
- A place where farmers can ask for help/questions
- A place for common storage
- A place which can facilitate interaction between different actors
- Something like reddit or Instagram
- Built on existing platforms like Facebook
- Something like Olivipedia

Knowledge

- It needs to be practical expertise that can inspire farmers to apply and innovate
- It should come from farmers, the common problems they experience defined at different levels
- It should be field based
- It should have clear targets
- It should be kept alive and updated
- It should provide answers to problems
- It should be adapted to end-user type
- It should provide a clear idea about problems
- It should be embedded in the everyday market
- It should clearly state at what level it was made
- It should clearly state why it was made
- It should be edited by advisor-experts
- It should be translated into practical knowledge
- It should tackle technological, economic and ecological problems

Collaboration

- There should be a common interest in innovation, such as a research institute
- It should be facilitated by a diverse community
- It should focus on co-creation
- There should be as many members as there are states
- There should be a EU TN defined by local groups
- It should help reconnect people to the food-chain, together with consumers
- It should involve noble farmers
- It shouldn't be about end users, but about partners
- There should be dynamic links at the national/EU-level with regular meetings
- There should be meetings in groups which involves traveling
- It should be a comfortable cooperation
- There should be active participation
- It should be about TNs just being together
- It should foster personal relations
- There should be governance goals and drive
- It should allow actors to stay connected

Communication & dissemination

- There should be the ability to meet farmers and exchange ideas
 - There should be videos of the best cases with co-created content
 - Local meetings and conferences should be used
 - Web TV should be set up to approach potential younger targets
 - There should be international showcases of new ideas
 - There should be cross-visits of different actors
 - We should talk about all actors as 'partners'
 - The content should be adapted to the member's state
 - There should be clear targets and no buzz words
 - It should be in the farmer's native language
 - There shouldn't be language barriers
 - It should allow farmers to communicate more with farmers
- **More**
- It should have more time, people and financing

- Training and support should be provided by the network
- It should do research set in the 21st century
- There should be an at EU-level TN
- It should detect problems and issues
- It should exist forever
- It should provide a clear overview of all TNs
- It should receive help from the government
- It should generate impact at a local level, but also at a regional-, national- and EU-level • It should map the end user needs

Cover Template: At the end of the group session the facilitator of each group created a summary of what was discussed in the group. In order to do this they had to fill in a cover template and present this to the plenary group.

Group 1

The ideal TN will use digital technology to create a place for interaction with experts and offer WebTV to engage young potential farmers. The created knowledge of the ideal TN will fit into a community of practice, delivering applicable knowledge to farmers. In the true spirit of collaboration, the ideal TN ceases to talk about end users, but will consider all involved actors as partners co-create knowledge and can learn from each other. The communication and dissemination of knowledge will happen in an understandable language where well-defined concepts are used instead of overgeneralised buzz-words.

The ideal TN will connect farmers to policy makers as well as consumers. Finally, the ideal TN will network by asking questions and showing interest, instead of dictating answers to farmers.

THE EURAKNOS JOURNAL

Issue Wednesday 11th September 2019

Digital

A place for interaction with experts
WebTV: Reaching young potential farmers

Knowledge

Euraknos and TNs are a community of practice, delivering applicable knowledge

THE IDEAL TN

Collaboration

No more end-users: Welcome partners!
Co-creation of knowledge
Training: let's learn from each other

Communication & dissemination

Say goodbye to buzz-words: on the importance of understandable language
Using well defined concepts
Connecting farmers and policy-makers
Interacting with consumers

And more!

How to make more friends by asking questions rather than providing answers

Group 2

- The ideal TN should have a clear and narrow focus on the problem it wants to solve within a certain sector by knowing (needs, problems, preferences & barriers) of end users and involving end users from the start. This could be done by linking with existing or by starting new OGs to do this via a bottom-up approach.
- It should have a flexible roadmap on the solutions the TN wants to develop and co-create this with the best experts that are required to solve the problem. These can come from different actors. But end users should also be involved in this process to ensure the user friendliness and the feasibility of the solutions that are being developed. As such, everybody should have a clear view on the process, the intermediate steps and their role within the process. This should be translated in some sort of TN 'Code Of Conduct' to clearly spell out expectations and roles. Moreover, additional resources should also be spent to create a culture of trust within a TN via team building to enforce the 'Code Of Conduct'.
- The co-creation process should be facilitated by expert facilitators only.
- In addition, the ideal TN should have a multi-layered structure in the network taking into account the regional, national and EU level from start to end.
- It should build and grow an interactive 'Community of Practice' that can refine the solutions and enhance the uptake in an iterative learning spiral by creating regional pilots and by A/B testing in different regions to take into account regional differences.
- It should provide digital support structures that allow to share problems, expertise, solutions and that can bring actors together. In addition, the digital platform should allow to profile users and only present content that is fit to their level of expertise and in their preferred language (automatic profiling and translation). Also, the platform should use user analytics to further optimize this + evaluations and feedback forms on the solutions and outputs it generates. This would allow the TN to improve them and adapt them, so they stay relevant
- (See the iterative spiral from the 'Community of Practice').
- Nonetheless, the ideal TN should also target 'analog users' and increase the digital literacy of their end users via training and taking into account the innovation adaptation curve.
- A lot of budget should be spent on actual dissemination, even in a separate project after the project has ended. Resources and (financial) incentives to engage end users are needed and to connect local OGs across members' states in a peer-to-peer fashion.
- The ideal TN should be sustainable and ensure that the project results stay available for the intended target audiences and beyond, even after the project has ended.

 THE EURAKNOS JOURNAL
Issue Wednesday 11th September 2019

Digital
A learning & sharing platform to support the community of practice & TN community
The future of results: searchable, profilable & automatically translated
Sustainability

Knowledge
Clearly defined problems!
Bottom-up approach with OG's
Flexibility in roadmap & solutions
Knowing & involving the relevant end users (problems, needs & preferences)

THE IDEAL TN

Collaboration
Sharing best practices through MAA with end users
Co-create the best solutions
Building an EU-community of practice: facilitation, learning, iteration & optimization
Involving all relevant partners
Incentivizing farmers

Communication & dissemination
Adapted communication: taking into account regional preferences of end users
Adequate time & resources
Digital & analog: All end users

And more!
How to co-create: Code of conduct on responsibilities, team-building & professional facilitation
Multi-layered structure: EU, national, regional

Group 3

Knowledge

- A TN should focus on figuring out the needs / right questions for different actors
- Farmers and advisors are also knowledge providers
- Therefore we need a 2-way knowledge exchange
- Knowledge output should be provided in tailored formats, specific to user profiles

Digital

- All output should be easily retrievable via a robust search engine
- An ideal TN should provide a toolbox that facilitates peer 2 peer sharing among farmers
- An ideal TN should function as an app for daily use

Collaboration

- TNs should cover all regions and countries EU-wide
- TNs should be dynamic: participants could change roles during the project
- TNs should have 'trust building' phase with partners, but also towards end users who need to get to know and trust a TN.

Communication and dissemination

- Communication & Dissemination should be via tailored channels, adapted to user profiles
- A TN should accommodate translations in language & format
- Communication channels & formats should be adapted to specific sharing goals
- There is a crucial role for National Rural Networks to act as multipliers (local & reach)

More

- TNs should have a longer period, to build trust among partners, compile knowledge & disseminate effectively

The ideal should ask the right questions relevant to all actors where farmers, foresters, and advisors help create the knowledge providing solutions focused on the needs of each actor. The ideal TN provides a 2-way knowledge exchange between actors. It should supply the digital means to facilitate this peer2peer knowledge exchange, by providing easy access to content through an optimised search engine as well as an app for daily use. The ideal TN should cover all countries EU-wide and allow actors to flexibly adapt

their role in the TN. To start off on the right foot, the ideal TN should start with a trust-building phase between actors. The ideal TN will communicate and disseminate knowledge to specific user profiles in a tailored way by taking into account their preferred formats and language, and with the specific goal of sharing knowledge. In order to achieve this, the ideal TN sees a crucial role of the NRN. Finally, the ideal TN will not be a short-lived project, but will run over a longer period allowing it to build stronger relationships.

 THE EURAKNOS JOURNAL
Issue Wednesday 11th September 2019

Digital
Finding knowledge easily: A search engine
Your go-to toolbox: P2P-sharing among farmers
Learn a bit more every day: our new app

Knowledge
Asking the right questions for all actors
The source: Farmers and advisors are knowledge providers
A 2-way knowledge exchange
Focus: the needs of each actor

THE IDEAL TN

Collaboration
Covering all regions and countries EU-wide
Dynamic TNs: participants changing roles
Trust me! The trust building phase of a TN

Communication & dissemination
The right fit: Tailored formats & channels specific to user profiles
Translations: language & formats adapted
The message: For specific sharing goals
The crucial role of NRR (local & reach)

And more!
Lifecycle: Longer period for a TN

17:15 - 17:30 Closing off day 1 for the participants

Presenter: Pieter Spanoghe

What have they learned, and what should they keep in mind for tomorrow.

Day 2 (9:00 - 17:15)

* *The presenters are expected to circulate amongst the 3 groups to answer possible questions and to communicate specific remarks to the facilitators.*

9:00 - 9:15 Introduction day 2

Presenter: Sylvia Burssens

Brief recap of day 1 and presenting the planning of day 2

9:15 - 9:45 Presentation on Communication & Dissemination *Presenter: Pauline Bodin*

9:45 - 10:45 Discussion about Communication & Dissemination in 3 different groups

Facilitators: Laurens Van der Cruyssen, Davino Van Hal and Nathan De Geyter

Transcribers: Elena Feo, Els Berckmoes and Merete Studnitz Expert: Pauline Bodin

Discussion

1. Question: Are you able to reach 60% of the unusual suspects of your target population (e.g. local farmers)?

· The group was separated into 3 groups (they don't know, they know and don't reach 60%, and they know and they do reach 60%; they can only say they know if they have explicitly measured it). The amounts were counted and subsequently each group member wrote down on a post-it their answer to the following questions related to their main answer:

a. They don't know:

- o What are the main reasons they don't know? b. They know and they don't reach 60%:
- o How did they measure it?
- o What are the main causes?

c. They know and they do reach 60%:

- o How did they measure it?
- o What are the main causes?

This exercise took between 20-25 minutes

<p>I DON'T KNOW... What are the causes for that?</p>	<p>I KNOW, BUT I DON'T REACH IT. How did you measure it?</p>	<p>I KNOW, AND I DO REACH IT. How did you measure it?</p>
	<p>What are the causes for <u>not</u> reaching it?</p>	<p>What are the causes for reaching it?</p>

Template: Are you able to reach 60% of the unusual suspects of your target population (e.g. local farmers)?

Results

Group 1

Question: Are you able to reach 60% of the unusual suspects of your target population (e.g. local farmers)?

- a. They don't know (11 participants) o What are the main reasons they don't know?
- Analytics do not differentiate between persistent non-engagers and usual audience
 - Face to face meetings claimed as best dissemination but the same people turn up, there's a peer bias.
 - It is difficult to identify newcomers and successors
 - There is often a focus on advisors
 - We're still a young TN, we haven't started the phase of C&D
 - Not measured yet because of the lack of the right tools and time, but will be done in the future.
 - Language difficulties
 - We don't know how to measure outreach
 - We don't know how to profile visitors/followers
 - Traditional farmers are not really open to new technologies which are communicated by specialists from EU-projects
 - Social media doesn't allow us to define occupation in a limited way as this is the user's decision to write their occupation.
 - Measuring system (SEO) couldn't define the visitors' occupation so it's impossible to define the exact audience.
 - We don't know because we don't have the time for strategic communication, to explain all aspects, and to organise information that needs to be communicated.
 - "60%" means that you have identified and listed all end users and kept track of all communication efforts/impacts (direct & indirect)
 - It wasn't measured by the project team.
 - Do we know enough about the end users? And is it possible to adapt our communication?

- Is effective outreach actually a parameter which is taken into account by funding agencies?
 - We emphasise informal knowledge exchange which is difficult to measure but important for the sustainability of the TN.
 - Our topic doesn't allow us to measure this as our potential end-users are all young people who could become farmers.
- b. They know and they don't reach 60% (2 participants) o How did they measure it?
- Lists of participants at events
 - Following web traffic
 - Google analytics, but this is not personalised o What are the main causes?
 - The meetings we organise contain people who are coming, not everybody we could reach
 - We don't have good tools to find out what the real response rate is
 - A lot of people simply don't have time to participate
 - Some users don't have broadband connection
 - Some users lack digital skills
 - Some users are simply not interested
- c. They know and they do reach 60% (1 participant) o How did they measure it?
- Extensive targeted market investigation before the project was in the main stage (continuation of several projects)
 - Systematic market investigation in several EU-projects done
 - Direct contact with a large number of farmers
 - Former EU-project continued in several languages
 - Continuation and interlinking
 - Getting feedback o What are the main causes?
 - Attitude: the product comes first
 - Problem solving organic farming
 - Innovative technology product solution offered
 - Increased market competitiveness of farmers

Conclusions

There is a lack of knowledge on how to measure outreach, as well as a lack of time and budget to measure the outreach. Measuring the outreach might not be conceptually possible in some cases and some potentially targeted end users will remain very difficult to reach. Finally, measuring outreach doesn't equate to generating impact.

Group 2

- o Do not know:
 - Some participants said that the target for C & D was never clearly defined and therefore not measured. Others said that it is difficult to measure, especially for the uptake of results and the measurement of indirect impact. How to distinguish your influence from others? Often there is not enough time and resources to do this properly, since the most results are only disseminated at the end of the project lifetime. II. Know, but unsuccessful:
 - Few participants said it is difficult to reach the 'hard-to-reach' profiles.
 - Sometimes there is no trust, nor an immediate benefit that can be demonstrated, which negatively impacts the uptake of results.
 - o Know and successful:

- Most participants said that they measured it during events and activities by the number of participants or with online materials by the website traffic, followers on social media, the number of registrants in a database or via the number of downloads or views of certain output material.
- Some TNs, such as 4D4F, measured it with user analytics in a learning community, but this created additional barriers, e.g. the need for registration.
- Agridemo-F2F did try to analyse impact by doing telephone interviews 6 months after the demos, but the results are currently being processed! (Follow up on results?!)
- The reason they were successful is because the activities were always targeted to a specific end user group with a narrow focus and adapted to their needs (local language, easy to understand).

Group 3

- Don't Know category
 - o Simply don't measure
 - o There is no target set
- Measure, but do not reach 60%
 - o We don't actually know the size of the population
 - o Reach is different to number of implementations
 - o Broad reach is difficult, because TNs don't have a direct connection
 - o There is a lot of competition in information channels for farmers
- **(how can we) Measure, do reach 60%**
 - o You need to set a target
 - o Needs to be region specific
 - o Interact with key players
 - o Lots of 'legwork' by the facilitator
 - o Choose partners with a broad reach / great connections
 - o Use existing partner channels
 - o Connect to existing OGs / Networks
 - o It takes time to get momentum in the MAA

2. Exercise on adapted communication and dissemination

The participants were presented with some examples of output of knowledge (the homepage of a TN-website, a LinkedIn-post by a TN and a video by a TN) which was disseminated to end users. They had to say whether they found the output suited for particular end users which were pre-defined (3 different profiles) and why it was or it wasn't. The reasons were noted on a poster by the facilitator. This took 25-30 minutes.

TN-website

Practice-led innovation supported by science and market-driven actors in the laying hen and other livestock sectors
 HORIZON 2020 ISIB-02-2014 project, Grant no. 652638

Welcome	The HENNOVATION project was the first thematic networks funded under the topic ISIB 2 'Closing the research and innovation divide: the crucial role of innovation support services and knowledge exchange' of the Horizon 2020 EU Research and Innovation programme; implemented from January 2015 to August 2017.
Project overview	Using the laying hen sector as a case study, the Hennovation project demonstrated the potential of innovation led by farmers and industry practices in two areas of concern, Injurious Pecking and End-of-Lay, during transport and at the abattoir. This was realised through the establishment of in total 19 innovation networks at different levels of the production chain, local, national and European level in five countries (United Kingdom, Sweden, The Netherlands, Spain and The Czech Republic). These networks proactively searched for and utilized new ideas to make their business more efficient and sustainable. These networks were supported by science driven-actors, such as veterinary surgeons, farm advisors and scientific researchers, and market-driven actors, such as those that buy eggs e.g. retailers, packers, food processors, and those certifying egg production (farm assurance, certification schemes). The overarching aim of these networks was to develop and disseminate innovations based on practice, and supported with economic and scientific information, to increase sustainability of the laying hen sector.
Project Results	The research work carried out as part of this project revealed that the practice-led approach promoted by the project can be a great stimulus for innovation. Alongside product or technical (e.g. new type of litter material to reduce stress and encourage natural behaviour or the use of alpacas in organic systems to reduce predation), a variety of often less expected and sometimes unintended 'soft' innovations also emerged through these networks. These were related to protocol or process (e.g. a new way of monitoring Poultry Red Mite infestation and new relationships between value chain actors, for example the pullet rearer).
Facilitating practice-led innovation	A variety of materials were developed for the support actors engaged with the networks. These included existing (scientific) as well as newly co-generated knowledge such as extension manuals on Feather Pecking and the End-of Lay, an online training course, 38 Practice Abstracts and five Technical notes. Guidelines for network facilitation and a Hennovation video, explaining the practice-led approach, were also developed to support network facilitators. All these materials can be found on this website.
Technical Resources	The work done by the project suggests that successful multi-actor, practice-led innovation networks depend upon active participation from all involved, professional facilitation , moderate resource support and access to relevant expertise . From the research works done it is also clear that opportunities and advantages exist for the development of a more facilitative and practice-led model of innovation with sustainable agricultural systems. And that recognising the value of this type of innovation as 'science' and its product as 'innovation' is a significant step in resolving the longstanding and enduring 'science/innovation gap'.
Laying-hen research priorities	
Partners	
Advisory Board	
Hennoventies	
News & Events	
Links	
Contact Us	

TN LinkedIn-post

Innoseta - Thematic Network
 90 abonnés
 7 mois

#Innoseta website is now available in all 7 Hub languages! Visit www.innoseta.eu and subscribe to our Newsletter to keep in touch!
 #spraying #equipment #training #advising #thematicnetwork #H2020

Voir la traduction

👍 5

👍 J'aime 💬 Commenter ➦ Partager

Soyez le premier à commenter ceci

TN video

Subsequently the participants could make suggestions on how to improve the examples which were written down on the poster by the facilitator. This part took about 5 minutes.

Profiles

Profile 1: Thomas is a 55-year-old livestock farmer from France who doesn't speak English and doesn't spend much time on the internet looking for innovative/sustainable solutions as it is often in English jargon. He generally uses a desktop computer, which runs Windows 7.

Profile 2: Alex is a 35-year-old Bulgarian wine farmer who tries to innovate as much as possible by looking online. He is digitally savvy and assembled his own desktop computer. He speaks English quite well and will know his way around jargon, but doesn't always have much time to look on the internet.

Profile 3: Gina is a 30 year old Italian forester, she speaks some English, but she notices that websites often use difficult words which cause her to make mistakes when trying to implement a solution found online, often she will try to find a forum where she can ask for more information. She has an iPhone and a laptop, and knows her way around social networks.

PROFILE 1	PROFILE 2	PROFILE 3
<p style="text-align: center;">EURAKNOS</p> <p style="text-align: right;">leapFORWARD ▶</p>		

Template: Adapted communication and dissemination

Results

Group 1

PROFILE 1	PROFILE 2	PROFILE 3
<p>1) Too much text, no images only in English, too complex, too much paper language, too paper forward, it's hard to address the frame</p> <p>2) English and LinkedIn (not intended) - social media not suited for multiple languages</p>	<p>1) not enough time, not find the best practices, that's not addressing primary producers</p> <p>2) probably included in LinkedIn important message but just a reference to a volume about what LinkedIn probably not for papers, focused more likely</p>	<p>1) //</p> <p>2) most likely included in list in</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">SUGGESTIONS</p> <p>1) work by themes -> application oriented</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> x short message x summarise x graphical layout x short video x links to social networks x more dynamic x add blog / od questions x regularly contact for frames <p>2) - add BIL to contact</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - use flags to give an idea of ed languages - link it through an influence paper in the board - your articles should be the message, not the newsletter - not half of the messages in tags - tags are too generic, not specific enough - tags should highlight the problem <p style="text-align: right;">leapFORWARD ▶</p>		

Example 1: WebsiteProfile 1: Thomas

- There is too much text and no images
- He doesn't speak the language and there is no translation • The content is too complex
- The content contains too much project language/jargon
- The website is too much focused on the project and possibly not of interest to people outside of the project
- Suggestion: Work by themes that could be of specific interest to Thomas and are easily identifiable and application oriented

Profile 2: Alex

- He doesn't have much time and it is not easy to find the best practices • The website is not addressing the primary producers enough
- Suggestion: The text on the homepage must have a short and clear message
- Suggestion: The content of the website should be more output oriented and with more graphs to be more convincing to Alex
- Suggestion: Add a short video to the homepage

Profile 3: Gina

- Similar remarks to the profiles of Thomas and Alex
- Suggestion: The website needs to link to social networks as this is what she's used to.
- Suggestion: The website needs to be more dynamic and less static
- Suggestion: directional profile, add blogs suggestions and ask questions • Suggestion: More engaging content

Example 2: LinkedIn postProfile 1: Thomas

- The post is on LinkedIn, in which Thomas is most likely not interested
- The post is in English, a language Thomas doesn't understand, and on social media language can be a very difficult to adapt to the user, especially in multilingual countries

Profile 2: Alex

- LinkedIn is probably not the best platform to reach farmers, Facebook is better
- The post is important but it is a reference to another website, and it's not clear about what
- Suggestion: Add a poll to the content to make it more engaging

Profile 3: Gina

- She is the most likely candidate to use LinkedIn
- Suggestion: Use flags instead of written text to communicate which languages are now available
- Suggestion: Link the post through an influencing figure on social media
- Suggestion: The articles should be the message, not the newsletter
- Suggestion: The message can't be made up of tags for 50%
- Suggestion: The tags are too generic and not specific enough (discussion in the group as to whether this is actually a bad thing)
- Suggestion: Tags should highlight the problem

Conclusions

- The presented content is not adapted to the needs of the different end users in terms of language and engaging content
- Clear choices need to be made regarding the platforms used to reach relevant end users
- These communication tools can allow more interaction with the end users by asking questions and gaining feedback
- Some end users will remain very difficult to reach

Group 2

- All farmers only interact and take up materials they trust or via people or channels they trust! This is especially true for the harder to reach profiles, such as profile 1. So, TNs need to create a community or leverage existing communities. Moreover, using existing channels, network organizations or relevant and known news outlets and media contacts, instead of reinventing the wheel is crucial. A mapping of relevant resources and contacts for TNs can be very interesting.
- In addition, TNs often naturally have a very specific focus on those that are willing to hear the message and those you can reach and use them as influencers to get a multiplication effect (go from easy to hard user profile according to the innovation adaptation curve). For example, in Belgium and the Netherlands only 2% of the farmers can be considered as innovators and
- Existing farm networks know who these are. TNs should focus there.
- In general, most projects take this innovation adoption curve into account and they first target and work with the farmers that are open for innovation (profile 3) and then they 'hope' that they will convince the early adopters (profile 2), who should convince the early and late majority (profile 1). However, a clear strategy with support tools to leverage this knowledge transfer effect is almost never in place.
- The use of professional teachers or a known and trusted education platform can be an added value.
- All messages need to be relevant to the point and instantly provide value. Therefore, the content should also be easily searchable and findable, e.g. via keywords (high signal to noise ratio within a max of 5 clicks).
- In terms of the format, the less text and the more visual and interactive the better. The actual content needs to be adapted to the local conditions (language) and to local farmers (expertise level), as much as possible. This makes the content more authentic and creates trust.

Group 3:

Twitter post

- In English, might not be understood by everyone
- Is Twitter the right channel?
- There is no 'Trigger' (why should I care / who is it directed to)
- It seems targeted at officials & other TNs ☹ is this the target?
- You might add hashtags (#TN, #Explanation)
- Add a picture as example

Front page

- Way too much text
- Not targeted at farmers
- Sidebar is too complex
- Use headlines / photos for a better reading experience
- Use easier wordings
- Rethink the information architecture

Video

- There is no context.
- Who is it targeted to?
- Why should I watch it?
- No clear communications

10:45 - 11:00 15min break

11:00 - 12:30 Presentation/workshop on Data & Content
 Presenter: Rosa Mosquera Losada

12:30 - 13:30 Lunch

13:30 - 14:00 Evaluation of the design of Knowledge Reservoirs within Thematic Network
 Presenter: Maxime Marois

14:00 - 15:00 Discussion on the design of Knowledge Reservoirs within Thematic Networks in 3 different groups
Facilitators: Laurens Van der Cruyssen, Davino Van Hal and Nathan De Geyter
Transcribers: Elena Feo, Els Berckmoes and Merete Studnitz
 Expert: Maxime Marois

Discussion

The plenary session was split up into 3 groups and the participants were presented with 5 different questions in sequence. Each participant had to write down his/her answer on a post-it and present it to the group. Each question could be discussed in group between 10-12 minutes.

Questions

1. *How do farmers/foresters communicate their needs to the TN?*
2. *Is all the output of a TN useful or should the e-KRP be selective? If so, based on which criteria? (innovation & sustainability)*
3. *What determines the level of expertise required to create & curate content?*
4. *Who should determine who gets to add content to the e-KRP?*
5. *Who should be responsible for transforming data in standardized (TN/e-KRP) format?*

Results

Group 1

Question 1: How do farmers/foresters communicate their needs to the TN?

- Through surveys and questionnaires, but these can be unreliable and there can be a sampling bias.
- Through meetings
- Through workshops
- Through regional groups key influencers
- Through intermediaries such as farmer organisations
- At stakeholder events
- Through contact with local network representatives
- They have to be contacted by a TN, they won't proactively communicate their needs

- Through an innovation audit by an innovation broker
- Through yearly national steering group meetings
- During farm visits, through direct dialogue
- By asking them

Conclusions

There is a need for a reflective exercise across the network as to what is a good way to detect farmer's needs. For instance, when a farmer becomes a member of an organisation, their characteristics could be asked and interesting information can be acquired. At regional meetings specific knowledge gaps can be identified. The participants suggested a need to use multiple channels in order to gain more knowledge about the farmer's needs.

Question 2: Is all the output of a TN useful or should the e-KRP be selective? If so, based on which criteria? (Innovation & sustainability)

- No, there needs to be a region of interest, funds need to be allocated properly and there needs to be replicability across areas
- The results need relevance to make a difference and create impact
- We shouldn't be selective, as long as there is online space available
- Innovation is time bound, some ideas might not be popular now, but they might become popular a bit later
- Results should be differentiated between general and country specific
- Regardless of the usefulness of the knowledge, the importance lies in the sharing of the knowledge, leaders will validate it
- All output is useful to some extent, different criteria should apply to different products/outputs
- Not all outputs could be useful, it depends on the needs
- Clear labelling is crucial, is the output a practice abstract, a case study or an opinion piece.
- TNs should provide relevant information
- There's a need for a clear framework for the interpretation of the output
- Farmers should be able to react to output

Conclusions

There was some discussion on whether all output should be allowed. If the knowledge base is too selective, interesting and innovative knowledge could be lost because it doesn't meet certain predefined criteria. If the knowledge base is not selective, then it needs to be very clear how specific output should be interpreted by means of clear labelling. There is also a risk that farmers might not want to share all relevant data on being innovative.

Question 3: What determines the level of expertise required to create & curate content?

- To create: the person needs to have subject knowledge and communication skills to be able to write output in a comprehensible way
- To curate: The person needs to know the audience for whom the content is meant
- It needs to be as open as possible
- There is a need for clear labels, is this scientific content or rather a radical idea
- There's a need for a validation process, which needs to be well defined at the beginning
- Only a few people can validate, which demands a lot of effort from these people and causes it to fail in the end
- Often the partners in the project don't care about the validation
- It is important to ask where the info will eventually end up

Conclusions

Setting up a process to curate and validate output might create the feeling that one is protected from inferior output quality, but this process is likely to fail, so it is better to clearly label output, which still requires a lot of time and effort.

Question 4: Who should determine who gets to add content to the e-KRP?

- Democracy is nice, but inefficient, a dictatorship will be a lot more efficient
- A mixed system such as Wikipedia is interesting because it allows the users to see the history of specific output, but it could also allow the user to signal that output is outdated and needs to be re-evaluated. But people will have to want this and get recognition for their efforts.
- There is a need for best practices on how to curate content
- There is a need to define a clear governance structure at the onset of the project

Conclusions

Regardless of whether this is determined in a democratic or dictatorial way, this needs to be clearly defined from the beginning and be done very transparently.

Question 5: Who should be responsible for transforming data in standardised (TN/eKRP) format?

- If this is done by a centralised unit, value can get lost
- There's a need for a degree of standardisation going from tailor-made solutions to highly standardised content depending on who the output is for • What will be transformed? The format or the text?
- There is also a way to standardise by theme or by country to better fit the needs of the end users
- Standardisation can happen of the front-end and/or the back-end, this can have an impact on the user-friendliness

Conclusions

The discussion mainly centred around what is understood by standardisation. Only when it is clear how output needs to be standardised and what exactly will be standardised, can it be determined who is able to do it.

Group 2

- There are several strategies that a TN can use to better elucidate end user (farmer/forester) needs and to build trust among end users. This is especially the case for strategy A, B and D.

- A. The first strategy is to involve end users in the partnership of the consortium. This implies that they should already be actively involved in the proposal-writing phase when the project concept and methodology are conceived.
- B. The second strategy is to organize workshops or scoping seminars with end users at the start of the project. This can be best done by involving local networks, like operational groups, multipliers (farm extension services or cooperatives) or by setting up regional nodes as local hubs to meet TN partners and share needs, information and potential solutions.
- C. The third strategy is to organize F2F interviews or perform a large-scale survey through existing networks or channels, e.g. existing farmer-consulting systems.
- D. One final innovative storytelling strategy was used by the TN Agrispin (Deliverable 1.5). They started by asking all partners of the consortium to write a story about a farm innovation that they were working on, their role, the journey they had taken so far and the lessons they had learned in their own words. Next, they also collected the dreams of participants during F2F workshops.
 - To the question if the e-KRP needs to be selective and by which criteria, participants agree that it does not need to be selective, as long as a very good filters are in place. Moreover, it is very difficult to make it selective, since certain TN outputs are only relevant to some people and not to others. To decide on this in advance is very difficult. Therefore, filters are needed, such as A) a good categorization with keywords (geography, sectors, themes, needs, expertise, solutions, content type, origin, date, etc.) when you want to browse and be inspired or B) a very good and narrow search function (like google) when you want to find specifically what you are looking for.
 - The FarmDemo hub that was set up by AgriDemo-F2F²⁵, PLAID and Nefertiti²⁶ uses questions, instead of keywords or categories to guide the users to the results that are most relevant for them.
 - Some say that additional search options or evaluation systems to better filter the content on the e-KRP could be very useful, such as user analytics, user reviews of content, content suggestions (e.g. Amazon function: user that were interested in this were also interested in these alternatives) or a ‘bot’ that helps you to the information you need by an interactive virtual conversation (Q&A).
 - To decide on the input, the filters and categorization of the content when it is first stored in the e-KRP, the partners or TNs that were involved in creating the content should be involved as much as possible, since they know best which categories and filters apply.
 - To help curate the content, the managers of the platform best decide based on user analytics and user feedback.
 - To determine data standards for the e-KRP should best be done by the EIP-AGRI Service Point.

Group 3

Question 1

Depends on the phases of a TN:

Before:

- Farmer organizations

At start

- Survey
- First meeting facilitated by a TN
- Workshop
- Farmer organizations

²⁵ <https://agridemo-h2020.eu/>

²⁶ https://nefertiti-h2020.eu/?page_id=4830&lang=nl

- Face to face interviews
- 'Be present'
- Reflections after all meetings
- Practice & science meetings
- Meetings is a great format during the project End of a TN
- Interviews for evaluation & next steps

Learnings

- What didn't work: ask via platform (not enough engagement on the platform)
- What did work: one-on-one. Need to test different formats from one-to-one, one-to-many, one-to-all, many-to-many, many-to-all, all-to-all.

Question 2

- Classified by potential use
 - o For farmers
 - o For other TN's
- All should be available (maybe in a 'short form')
- Only proven best practices (this could be a **separate category**)
- *What is proven? (used = proven?)*
- # downloads = indication of interest & validity
- Should have different versions of content (long, short, video, audio,...) **user-specific content**

- Project-related information should only be on the TN website (technical info)
- It should not be a 'network-based' knowledge reservoir, but a 'content based' knowledge reservoir.

Learnings

What didn't work: ranking by end users

Check:

- 'Operational Group Requirements' = checklist
 - o Show 'failures' might seem an idea, but this could lead to commercial legislation.

Question 3

Create:

- Content should be created by the MAA, led by the consortium
- TN is responsible

Evaluate:

- Funding bodies should evaluate (it is at their request)
- Internal evaluation by the consortium + partners
 - o *Should user validation be a part of this or 'on top' afterwards?*

Learnings

- ADD: describe the 'condition' in which the innovation works well. Now it is regularly only the technology, too little context
- Legal dispute on showing 'failures'

Question 4

- Coordinator or Staff

- Management Board

Who's in charge for translations?

Question 5

- Database: standardized formats
- TNs should be part of the project o There is a different way of working for new vs. existing TNs

15:00 - 15:30 30 min break

15:30 - 16:00 Presentation on Multi Actor Approach Presenter: Elodie Pascal

16:00 - 17:00 Discussion in Multi Actor Approach in 3 different groups

Facilitators: Laurens Van der Cruyssen, Davino Van Hal and Nathan De Geyter

Transcribers: Elena Feo, Els Berckmoes and Merete Studnitz

Expert: Elodie Pascal

Discussion

1. Question: TN's mainly consider farmers and farmer advisors as possible actors within the MAA, what other end users should TN's consider more often? And why?
 - The participants got 2-3 minutes to write down which other actors are interesting and why on a post-it. Subsequently the participants presented their suggestion(s) to the group and hung it/them on a poster. Clusters were formed when specific actors were mentioned several times. Of main interest was when specific actors were mentioned several times for different reasons. This exercise took about 10-15 minutes in total.
2. Question: What type of (other) difficulties did you experience with regard to the MAA?
 - The participants mentioned the difficulties they experience with regard to the MAA while the facilitator wrote them down on a poster. The difficulties from the previous presentation of T2.4 were also mentioned by the facilitator if the participants didn't mention them. Subsequently, the participants voted on the most important difficulties they would like to resolve. This part took take 5-10 minutes.
3. Question: How can we overcome these difficulties?
 - The participants were paired and got a solution card which they could use to describe their idea to resolve one or more of the difficulties. Once they had filled in the card, they had present it to the group. This part took about 40 minutes.

Template: Difficulties

SOLUTION CARD

Make a sketch of your solution concept?

→ **Solution name**

→ **For who?**

→ **Why?** (Which difficulty are you avoiding/solving?)

→ **How?** (What is the solution? How does it work?)

Template: Solution card

Results

Group 1

Question: *TNs mainly consider farmers and farmer advisors as possible actors within the MAA, what other end users should TN's consider more often? And why?*

- Value chain players and industry
- Consumers: to educate them about agriculture
- Administration: as they often form an important threshold
- Policy makers
- Media: to communicate the importance of agriculture
- Researchers
- Students: as potential farmers and foresters
- Teachers
- Young entrepreneurs
- Farmers associations
- Ecotourism: as branding (vacation at a farm) and a different business model
- Activists: in order to prevent potential thresholds and co-create possible solutions
- Capital providers
- Professionals: to provide expert knowledge often lacking in TNs

Question: *What type of (other) difficulties did you experience with regard to the MAA?*

- Understanding each other (communicating science to farmers) (4 votes)
- Budget, more actors means more expenses, it's hard to have an oversight of costs (1 vote)
- Alignment towards the same goal (6 votes)
- Digital communication/reliability (2 votes)
- Timing of activities, difficult to reach farmers during harvesting time or students during summer (8 votes)
- Time from stakeholders (7 votes)
- Engaging actors (4 votes)
- Stakeholder fatigue (no votes)
- Different levels of dedication (4 votes)
- Farmers have rigid minds, they don't want to change things that have always been done in that way (no votes)

Conclusions

The participants of group 1 considered the available time from stakeholders, the alignment of the different actors towards the same goals and understanding each other the main difficulties to tackle in order to achieve a better the MAA.

Group 2

- I. The type of actors that are important for a good MAA and that can also be considered as end users are
- A. Networks or organisations of farmers, like operational groups, cooperatives, regional networks, rural networks,
 - B. Researchers
 - C. Policy makers

- D. Teachers
- E. Media
- F. Industrial suppliers (feed, seed, fertiliser, agrochemicals, machinery, etc.)
- G. The entire value chain (traders, processors, retailers, consumers,...)
The reasons for this are that some are required to create an enabling environment for the actual implementation, such as proper regulation, but this is dependent on the type of TN output.
- II. Difficulties:
 - A. Time
 - B. Budget
 - C. Proper incentives for each actor, but especially for end users
 - D. Need for experienced facilitators
 - E. Need for open-minded actors
 - F. Different languages and expertise levels
 - G. Different needs for each actor
 - H. How to get engagement outside the partner countries of a TN
 - I. How to express the voice of all actors
 - J. How to avoid friction between competitors
- III. See solution cards

Group 3

1. The type of actors that are important for a good MAA and that can also be considered as end users are:

- TN = science + practice
- Focus more on farmers!
- Now TNs & OGs are focused too much on 'privileged farmers' (usual suspects). Should focus on others too
- All actors in the value chain are important (**decide who's relevant**)
 - Policy Makers
 - National Rural Networks (can disseminate)
 - Others: insurance industry vets,...
- More focus on SMEs
- Players that make the change

Learnings

- It is the TNs role to decide on supporting actors
 - Decide who is relevant
 - Timing is important
 - Important to stay independent

Ideas

- Include professionals for communications
 - Professional Journalist / Researchers
 - Communications agency

Question: How can we overcome these difficulties?

Solution cards

S1

Use an award for alignment, a newbie award for stakeholders in the network. Every partner country gives a yearly award.

Why: Because the stakeholders have to agree on the best criteria for the best business model, so they'll need to discuss the goal.

S2

Facilitation skills for all actors, by making a facilitator part of the consortium (soft skills).

Why: To bring all actors together and make them work together, everybody needs to remain engaged and seen, and contribute.

Additional: Facilitation networks to solve common problems and educate facilitation.

S3

A common time schedule for all actors.

Why: Because it is difficult to gather all actors.

Additional: They could meet at a farm.

S4

Power of actors. Agreements from the beginning. Clear vision on activities, participation and decision process (before the project/activities starts). One-on-one conversations with the main coordinator to start building trust. For the whole project to go well.

Why: So no one would feel left out/used/run over.

S5

Methodologies for MAAs handbook with practical examples for coordinators, partners and team facilitators. This should be based on actual practices and validated regularly.

Why: To achieve a common understanding of the approach, better organisation of project activities, and being effective in implementing the MAA.

S6

The right actors-partners. A good preliminary analysis of the subject and potential partners/actors based on previous experience and trust.

Why: The right actors are crucial for the success of the project.

S7

Getting specialised non-agricultural partners (e.g. facilitators) involved from the start. Why: Because you need to have the right people in the right place.

S8

Facilitation skills. Including one main expert facilitator per country who is very willing to do this. Who can provide 1 week training and set up inspiration and evaluation meetings (1 per year?) Why: To keep actors engaged and to support the MAA.

S9

Facilitation skills training for the functioning and success of the TN.

Why: To build or repair trust within a TN. To determine the actors and set goals and expectations and create a clear vision. To keep actors and end users engaged. To capture TN activities/issues and solve them. To prevent roadblocks and keep the network energised and functioning as well as working together. To keep innovation trials on track methodology of innovation development. Additional: Innovation spiral (see photo)

S10

Actors engagement by giving stakeholder simple solutions to real life problems. Organising practical visits to real farms to see problems they had and how they solved it. Why: Lack of interest and imagination of stakeholders.

S11

Define needs and connect users to their engagement, by defining and clustering needs (across regions, but keep aligning point).

Why: To increase engagement & improve project results, impact and sustainability.

S12

Thinking of potential benefits for each stakeholder such as money, showcase, publicity, teaching material, knowledge. This depends on each stakeholder.

Why: To increase motivation.

S13

The coordinators and partners have to be honest about the budget and ask other TNs how much they spend on what, what they've learned from previous mistakes, and assume that everything has a cost (such as monitoring & education).

Why: To create long-term sustainability, have a higher impact and better implementation.

S14

Prioritization of activities by the stakeholders.

Why: Because there is a lack of time.

S15

Timing of the engagement with a calendar and clock. Consider availability as a function of the cycle of nature (respect nature, respect farmers), create a common calendar. Respect the local habits with regard to timing (event start and end around lunchtime).

Why: Because availability is crucial.

S16

Farmer's participation, by making use of intermediaries and using social research methodology and mapping the flow of information.

Why: To increase impact.

S17

Regular feedback loops on work-packages of all actors by organising meetings and activities (with the whole network not only for facilitators and practitioners).

Why: Because lacking awareness of the process and one's role in the process.

S18

Networking between actors by doing visits together and allow time for networking as well as a devoted social media presence.

Why: To make them feel like more of a community.

S19

Story telling by collecting stories, stimulate people to write them down (moderation). Why: Illustrate what processes are all about and how they could intervene.

S20

Incentive4balance, events (field visits, meetings, boot camps) where actors present problems and receive solutions from peers. Creating a farming Hackathon Why: To balance the giving and taking.

S21

Time, money and better organisation. Increase the time and budget of TNs and OGs. Why: Because time is money.

S22

Find multiplier actors and appropriate national/regional networks.

Why: To relay findings/infos from TN to target group and engage outside TNs/countries

S23

Engage and express all voices from outside (real farm context), by using different methods, and providing equal opportunity to be heard (create the right setting)

S24

Engaging outside countries and partners by having a set proportion and budget that can be allocated in the first year of the project.

Why: To extend impact geographically and technically.

S25

The right budget for events by allocating enough budget for travelling and translation. Why: To allow foreign actors to attend international events.

S26

Hunt for open-mindedness by mapping the needs of farmers, advisors, policy makers and researchers, and teaming them up so as to help them develop skills they do not possess adequately. Why: To find open-minded actors to promote sustainable innovation.

S27

Provide training and coaching in order to connect by creating a trainers pool, organising trainings in different countries, creating a network and create actions towards enabling community. Why: To increase awareness about MA processes and to provide tools to steer energy.

S28

Search for innovators, finding open-minded actors by asking other partners. Why: Because they are the ones that have the innovations to be shared.

S29

Identify early adopters, how to involve farmers by calling them, asking for recommendations and networking.

Why: To identify best practices to share (peer learning).

S30

Farmers time, involve farmers from the beginning of the project as a partner by finding them during the partnership setting-up.

Why: Because it can save budget, time and increase engagement.

S31

Incentivise farmers by providing the possibility to pay for their time and ending replacement labour. Why: To encourage farmers to disseminate their innovation where they do not lose the commercial benefit.

S32

OFP = Organise a flexible process by defining groups of actors, organising good formats and installing reflection moments.

Why: Because that way less attention needs to go to the process. (See photo)

S33

Experienced facilitator, finding the correct person by selecting a person that is able to have both perspectives, show empathy, and talk appropriately to different actors with an already created network.

Why: Because having the correct person in the correct place makes the difference.

17:00 - 17:15 Closing off day 2 for the participants

Presenter: Pieter Spanoghe

What have they learned, what should they keep in mind for tomorrow.

17:15 Taskforce on the Future TN came together to discuss possible topics to present during the Future TN workshop. *Presenter: Laurens Van der Cruyssen*

Day 3 (9:00 - 12:30)

9:00 - 9:15 Introduction day 3 (small recap of day 1 and 2, and planning of day 3)

Presenter: Merete Studnitz

9:15 - 11:00 The Future TN Part 1

Facilitators: Laurens Van der Cruyssen, Davino Van Hal and Nathan De Geyter The facilitators started by presenting the results of the ideal TN exercise of day 1 to the plenary group. Subsequently the plenary group was divided into 9 groups of 4 participants. Each group had to discuss and describe the future TN with regard to specific questions, categories and topics

Questions

Which tasks does your TN still expect to do itself in the future TN?

What will your TN outsource to EURAKNOS?

What will your TN look like when dealing with (specific topic) bearing in mind that there is a digital TN platform?

Please keep these categories in mind:

- Content
- Platform (features)
- Communication & dissemination
- MAA
- Sustainability

Specific topics:

- *Climate change*
- *Generational renewal*
- *New business models*
- *New technologies and innovations*
- *Circular economy*
- *Digitization*

Article: The future TN

Which tasks does your TN still expect to do itself in the future TN?

What will your TN outsource to Euraknos?

What will your TN look like when dealing with climate change bearing in mind that there is a digital TN platform?

Please keep these categories in mind

Content

Platform (features)

Communication & dissemination

Multi-Actor Approach

Sustainability

leapFORWARD ▶

Template: The future TN

11:00 - 11:15 15min break

11:15 - 12:15 The Future TN Part 2

Facilitator: Laurens Van der Cruyssen

Transcriber: Elena Feo

Each group presented their future TN in a timeslot of about 6-8 minutes each

Results*

Group 1

From a TN we would like to define and choose the topic and define the actors to involve. We will manage that by involving people and being dynamic. That is what we keep in term of the MAA. The content creation and how we tailor it will be done during the lifetime of the TN by the consortium. In terms of communication and dissemination: webpage, newsletters, meetings, seminars, workshops and social media will be organized with the actors of the TN. What we hope that Euraknos can give us, is a Knowledge reservoir where it is possible to find practical solutions, a platform to store knowledge. This should be done in a collaborative way. We need to be able to define metadata and tag the content that we want to put online. This needs to be easy and friendly to use, without many barriers and with a list of contacts so people can identify who provided the content. In addition, the possibility to have feedback reports on how to use the knowledge reservoir should be developed. Also, content alerts, which means that every time there is something new the community should be informed about it, should be included. So, Euraknos should ensure end-user satisfaction and TN community satisfaction. What EURAKNOS can also do is to translate the content, e.g. documents, in all other languages. EURAKNOS can also provide useful templates and guidelines on how to best perform the MAA, guidelines on how to best use social media, social science methodologies, social science resources and social science experts, so the TNs can improve the engagement of the actors. Identify all the media channels and contacts in terms of TN communication in a media list.

<https://youtu.be/s5VJ0wDrfKM>

Group 2

The main goal of our future TN, Habit.Act, is to change the habits of all actors, i.e. consumers and farmers, in order to have an impact on climate change. We will focus on mixed farming systems and we will work with different actors involved in order to share experiences. For the MAA we focus on free local clusters to avoid language barriers, in 3 countries, where we have one cluster each. There is a coordinator in each cluster: a social scientist, both as a coordinator of the project and as a facilitator, because we want to have someone that can make a good connection between the different actors. Then we involve farmers, consumers, NGOs, trainers, policy makers and journalists to disseminate to the public in the local language. English will only be used for general consortium meetings and for the policy brief aka dissemination to policy makers. Knowledge will be adapted for different end users. We will create specific knowledge for farmers about the mixed farming system, for consumers about the farm in general, for researchers, etc.. We will follow EURAKNOS templates and guidelines in order to have a continuation and not reinvent the wheel. Local languages and English will be used for dissemination. For the e-platform, we aim to share experiences by recording activities so everybody can have a look on what is going on at a farm. We also want to create e-learning for students and farm games for children on how a farm functions. We also want to connect peers with the creation of “Farminder” (like Tinder) and a chat feature to ensure that consumers and farmers can exchange problems, solutions and ways of working together. In terms of C & D, we will use EURAKNOS as a channel, so to boost our reach via the social media of EURAKNOS, its newsletter and the policy connection. However, we want to have the added value solutions implemented locally, as opposed to EURAKNOS, which is more implemented as a network at international level. We also want to organize cross visits between different local clusters and demonstration days for consumers. We would also like to encourage farmers to spend some days in other farms abroad as an exchange programme with a farm holiday agency as a business model. We also want to involve consumers that they can directly invest in farmers that are producing locally.

<https://youtu.be/SydBwtAkySU>

Group 3

In the TN “Future For Beef” we will develop a tool to reduce carbon emissions and to increase feed conversion efficiency, called Verify Emissions, Gasses And Nutrition aka “VEGAN”. We will involve a variety of actors aka ‘Beef Stakeholders’, such as end users, farm organization, applied universities, (beef) industries, specialists in communication and dissemination. We will also have a steering group and

advisory board. We will organize two kick off meetings, one for stakeholders, one for the involved farmers. We will align them in the project and make sure that everyone is going in the same direction and to meet project deadlines. After two years, we will organize an international symposium where we will present results and together with other relevant TNs and OG. Related to content: we start with a consumer survey, after that we will develop C & D project videos to show our progress, including a state-of-the-art forum with state-of-the-art research. After that we will proceed with the tool development, best practice guides and links to OGs in Europe to develop the tool in Europe. We will also organize a best-practice award across Europe in 28 countries. We will create a Knowledge Reservoir to create content and pass it on to EURAKNOS that can disseminate it further. We will use a social media community reservoir. EURAKNOS can also help us link to OGs and provide templates for C&D so we can adapt them for our own project and make our results more visible. EURAKNOS can also provide a ‘white label’ platform that we can use and customize it to promote our own results and data during the project. Afterwards this can be integrated with the results of other projects in a centralized database. Build our own website. To make sure it is sustainable, we can build a business model and ensure farmers can use it in the future, make it “future proof” and make sure that the platform is implemented by the farmers themselves. Have connection between partners and local products where there is beef production. Start with a core group of partners, but then add partners during the lifetime of the TN. EURAKNOS should also provide templates and services for everything that is common for all TNs, such as data management and storage, C & D, etc.

<https://youtu.be/qWGRQHbrXqU>

Group 4

Our TN wants to collaborate with EURAKNOS as a generalized international entity or standard, but wants to keep its own identity. Therefore, we want to keep control of the formation of the consortium, the multi-actors to be invited, the type of knowledge collected in the TN, the shared vision of the TN. However, there is added value of working with a huge, centralized Knowledge Repository. We want to provide knowledge and data to a EURAKNOS platform, but it should not be a simple duplication of content (copy from website). It should add more value and create an experience to do something as a designated destination. For example, with different learning modules based on the TN knowledge library, such as on pig farming, arable farming or organic farming. So, to provide custom courses based on the knowledge libraries from the TNs, where farmers or other end users could learn and even get certificates. It could also add an interactive forum for peer-to-peer learning and provide coaching services for how to engage the next generation of farmers and have them interact with older generations. Besides fora for end users, a forum for TNs to foster peer-to-peer learning would also be interesting to support the next generation of TNs. EURAKNOS should build the back-end and functionality of this platform. All services should be free for the first 3 years during the life of the TN and the value should be established by the TNs and involved farmer organisations. Afterwards different business models and subscription services for those farmer associations could be explored to keep the content up-to-date and demonstrate the added value in the future. Normally dissemination peaks after content creation at the end of the TN, but thanks to EURAKNOS this level might decrease later or even increase.

<https://youtu.be/HVtOBsopE30>

Group 5

TNs will last more than the established years, e.g. one extra year to maintain the Knowledge Reservoir and to check the impact of the TN. To do this interviews and surveys could be done to check if farmers actually implemented new business models and solutions. We will also check what farmers really want and provide them with easy and understandable videos and materials with advice. We will organize farm demonstration and networking days to connect farmers, especially young farmers that are implementing new technologies. We will also give networking tips to connect with other farmers. We expect that EURAKNOS will give us some templates on what materials work and what not and a toolbox to look to specific information. We will promote a contest between young farmers to implement innovative ideas.

We will use different adapted channels and moving labs on how the actual situation on the farm is. Finally, we will also create a platform to help farmers to have better equipment by exchanging and renting it out.

<https://youtu.be/j6afCyae5W8> Group 6

We want to tackle two things that are quite contrary: having EURAKNOS saying “we know everything about TNs” and at the same time be very specific based on the users and selection criteria that is needed. How to approach this more systematically? Provide some agreed and obligatory first level of the repository. In this way it is easier to overcome the language barrier. And give the versatility and specifics to TN leaders to communicate. Having responsible players in each step of the system. The future TN is the network that receives the benefit of EURAKNOS, they will set and make use of the strategy by using resources of someone else. Let general public of users of EURAKNOS repository to make their vision of the business plan. In the end, everybody should be searching on EURAKNOS. Having something like google (simple in interface, but all knowing). Push notifications, based in certain criteria, could also be developed.

<https://youtu.be/gVQVyPYxVOA>

Group 7

Looking to a future TN after EURAKNOS has been setup in 5 years. The content will be unchanged because EURAKNOS will always be EU scale. The networks have to be always local and national. This is something the consortium will do themselves. EURAKNOS will help to standardize the content that is created by TNs by developing designated tools + explanation on how to use the tools to ensure consistent dissemination. EURAKNOS should continue the network after the project. This should ideally be user specific and dynamic. It is essential to specify where the TN will go after the end of the project. Create a website that merges all the websites of TNs, so visitors of one TN will also visit the websites of other TNs and get the bigger picture. And having an umbrella system will be easier to find actors in other projects, like social scientists or designers, or types of training, that will be supervised by an administrator (TN coordinator). EURAKNOS could help in the sustainability of the TN.

<https://youtu.be/RITvDOs7ay0> Group 8 Our TN is called ‘Food for future generation’. The project starts with a core group who really carry the ideas. We will start with a basket of questions (no answers). Next, we need to find allies and EURAKNOS can help with this. So, people that really like the idea of joining the TN from different stakeholders groups, like farmers’ consumers, retailers, schools, local governments, researchers etc. This is what we call the warm network of people that share an ambition to find solutions, not representatives. Next, we need to formulate a proposal involving the cold network that have to open possibilities, like managers and representatives. They have their own interests and targets and they can add their own questions to the basket to feed in the proposal to submit to Brussels. We need to keep all these actors involved before the approval and implementation of the project proposal. The main thing in the proposal is that you need to include space to explore and to grow and discover. It is important to brainstorm with young generation and analyses data statistics, find the right expertise, etc. Build a network that can sustain after the project period to ensure sustainability and to keep fuelling the movement. Also important to keep the cold network online. <https://youtu.be/eLIVIKs9tw>

Group 9

EURAKNOS can provide technical support, such as contacts to experts, like IT specialists for technical support. EURAKNOS can also provide the right contacts, collecting all regional advisors contacts and facilitators. That way TNs can build on each other’s networks. The same advisor can cover different networks and gain more expertise. Co-creation of knowledge by using key existing partners. Use the database of EURAKNOS to know what is existing about technical information (so we can prioritize as a new TN) and communication channels that work very well. In this way we don’t have to redo things that actually already exist. This will help save time. TNs can also include new business models after the project is done.

<https://youtu.be/v9BLZngPLJE>

*: transcripts have been slightly edited to enhance readability.

12:15 - 12:30 Closing off day 3

Presenter: Pieter Spanoghe

12:30 - 13:30 Lunch

13:30 - 15:30 Consortium related discussions

1. What did we learn from this meeting?
 - a. Regarding to content
 - b. Regarding to process
2. What do we want to repeat and avoid for the next workshop?
3. Time schedule for milestones and deadlines the rest of 2019
4. Varia

